

D2.1

The COLLABS Level-3 Security Package for Secure Digital Supply Networks: MVP

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Abstract:	<i>This deliverable is the first output of Work Package 2 tasks T2.1 (Tools and methods for secure data sharing), T2.2 (Trustworthiness of data flows), T2.3 (Machine learning-based cognitive security framework), T2.4 (Statistical Analytics and Machine- / Deep-Learning on shared data), T2.5 (Distributed anomaly detection for Industrial IoT) and T2.6 (Workflow-driven security for supply chain and compliance in manufacturing) related to the minimum viable product of the project. It describes and demonstrates the various technologies that form the COLLABS Level-3 security package for secure digital supply networks.</i>
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Executive Summary

The COLLABS project aims at developing, demonstrating, and supporting a comprehensive cyber-intelligence framework for collaborative manufacturing. This enables the secure data exchange across the digital supply chain while providing high degrees of resilience, reliability, accountability, and trustworthiness. It addresses threat prevention, detection, mitigation, and real-time response.

This deliverable provides a specification of the components and supporting tools and technologies in the minimum viable product (MVP) implementation of the COLLABS Level-3 security package for secure digital supply networks. These components are implemented through activities within the six tasks of work package 2. This third level of security mechanisms (1) comprises c tools for secure data sharing, ensuring trustworthiness of data flows in collaborative manufacturing environments, (2) delivers a machine learning-based cognitive security framework applied to shared data, and (3) deploys a workflow-driven security framework for supply chain and compliance in manufacturing based on distributed ledgers.

After the introduction, in chapter 2 we give an overview of the aspects of the COLLABS architecture addressed by Level-3 security. Then, in chapter 3, we describe the components of the COLLABS framework that implement Level-3 security for the MVP version of the system. In chapter 4, we present supporting methods for screening and improving the security of present and forthcoming COLLABS solutions that have not been developed and structured as components of the system. In chapter 5, we give an overview of the architectural framework for trustworthiness assurance. The final section concludes the deliverable.

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1. Introduction

Security within the COLLABS framework is organized into three levels, namely: Level 1 - hardware-enabled and device-level security, Level 2 - Inter-device level security based on distributed ledger technologies, and Level 3 - Machine learning-based cognitive security level. The aim of this deliverable is to provide an overview and description of components and supporting tools and technologies relevant to the MVP implementation of the COLLABS Level-3 security package for secure digital supply networks.

The identified objectives that the COLLABS Level-3 security package needs to achieve are providing tools for secure data sharing, ensuring trustworthiness of data flows in collaborative manufacturing environments, delivering a machine learning-based cognitive security framework applied to shared data, and deploying a workflow-driven security framework for supply chain and compliance in manufacturing based on distributed ledgers. For more details about the objectives of COLLABS Level-3 security please see deliverable D1.3.

Work on the COLLABS Level-3 security package permeates all tasks of Work Package 2, A secured digital supply network in collaborative manufacturing environments:

T2.1, Tools and methods for secure data sharing, deals with the required hardware and software architectures. It introduces the notion of trusted execution environment (TEE) and explains the concepts relevant to TEE functional availability in a device. The task addresses methods to remotely and dynamically manage TEEs, safe means to facilitate multiparty analytics of sensitive data, as well as security of the data from unauthorised access, and the anonymisation of the data.

T2.2, Trustworthiness of data flows, addresses the detailed design and development of the building blocks composing the trust infrastructure. To achieve this, the components and results developed in multiple other tasks are leveraged and combined, including machine learning, deep learning, and anomaly detection, with more details given in Section 5 of this deliverable.

T2.3, Machine learning-based cognitive security framework, is concerned with developing the core of the Level-3 security mechanism. This includes behavioural models that will enable the analysis of the network flows among multiple IoT devices. This is supported by methods for device identification and wireless fingerprinting based on features derived from packet headers as opposed to packet payloads, thus, facilitating use on both encrypted and non-encrypted network traffic. More details about the work done on this framework are given in Section 3.1.

T2.4, Statistical analytics and machine- / deep-learning on shared data, will offer privacy-preserving storage and analytics to end-users and enterprises by allowing seamless integration and injection of heterogeneous data, and facilitate the adoption of collaborative analytics to enterprises, without exposing private or sensitive information. More details about the work done within this task given in Section 4.2.

T2.5, Distributed anomaly detection for industrial IoT, advocates the introduction of intrusion detection systems (IDS) which are not limited to the local view of the device or a group of devices they are installed on, but rather employ a lightweight and distributed approach that leverages innovative machine-learning techniques to detect specific security threats and identify malicious behaviours. The work on this task is addressed in Section 5.2 of this deliverable.

T2.6, Workflow-driven security for supply chain and compliance in manufacturing, provides a workflow framework for security and resilience in collaborative manufacturing, allowing users to organise

production processes across companies in a secure manner. To achieve this objective, the task implements formalisation of contractual obligations and of security and compliance requirements. It integrates data streams from trustworthy sensors and provides concepts for enforcing the workflows in the secured collaborative manufacturing supply chain, leveraging technologies such as homomorphic encryption, distributed ledgers, blockchain, and distributed databases. Section 4.3 of this deliverable is relevant to this task.

Within the COLLABS trust infrastructure, the components and tools that facilitate data protection, developed in WP2, will consider both data in transit and data at rest. An important part of the infrastructure is the definition of an encrypted data flow model that specifies the use of cryptographic primitives, enabling data from IoT devices to be securely transferred and processed in trusted execution devices or end cloud-services.

The rest of the deliverable is structured as follows.

Section 2 gives an overview of the aspects of the overall COLLABS architecture that are addressed by Level-3 security for the MVP.

Section 3 describes the components of the COLLABS framework that facilitate Level-3 security, relevant to the MVP, which encompasses the machine learning-based cognitive security framework, statistical analytics and machine- / deep-learning on shared data, and workflow-driven security for supply chain and compliance in manufacturing.

Section 4 presents the supporting methods for screening and improving the security of present and forthcoming COLLABS solutions that do not necessarily constitute fully-fledged components of the system, and includes methods and guidelines for oblivious machine learning, distributed anomaly detection for industrial IoT, and the formal specs verifier (FSV).

Section 5 overviews the architectural framework for trustworthiness assurance and describes its main building blocks: Secure elements, data protection, and encrypted traffic analysis. Within the topic of data protection, details are provided on the data flow model specification, as well as specific associated scenarios provided by three project partners (initially described in deliverable D1.3), namely by ALES (S1 - controlled and secure remote maintenance, S2 - controlled share of compliance data, S3 - trusted compliance data share across the supply chain, S4 - analysis of manufacturing performance on a global scale), PCL (S1 - shop floor threat detection and prevention, S2 - remote data sharing), and REN (S1 - controlled and secured remote maintenance, S2 - cloud-based architecture for industrial processes, S4 - security of connected devices).

Finally, Section 6 concludes the deliverable.

2. Level-3 Security Components Relevant to the MVP of the COLLABS Architecture for Secure Digital Supply Networks

The third level of security of the COLLABS Architecture for Secure Digital Supply Networks (explained in more detail in Section 1 and deliverable D1.3) includes the components that have the ability to supervise information exchange between the devices either within the boundaries of the smart factory, or external partners within the digital supply network. By monitoring various data flows from the connected devices and creation of situational awareness they will be capable of anticipating security risk situations and activating prevention mechanisms. According to technology and mechanisms, the Level-3 security components could be divided into three main functional groups:

- *Group 1: Machine Learning-Based Cognitive Security Framework* - aims to develop behavioural models that will enable the analysis of the network flows among multiple IoT devices. It amalgamates the components: IoT Secure Wireless Fingerprinting and ML S(N)C Optimization and GMS Tools. The first one is based on scanning fingerprint information of multiple IoT devices, while the second one uses Machine Learning (ML) / Deep Learning (DL) models that enable the analysis of their behaviour.
- *Group 2: Statistical Analytics and Machine- / Deep-Learning on Shared Data* - will offer integration of heterogeneous data of the end-users and enterprises, and facilitate the adoption of collaborative analytics to enterprises without exposing private or sensitive information. It presents the synergy of the components named Security Infusion and 3ACEs.
- *Group 3: Workflow-Driven Security for Supply Chain and Compliance in Manufacturing* - will provide a workflow framework based on distributed ledger technology for security and resilience in collaborative manufacturing.

Besides these components, additional methods for screening and improving security will empower the COLLABS Architectural Framework. Their roles will be to leverage powerful cryptographic tools to protect the ML and DL algorithms; to manage, monitor and control the infrastructure and industrial processes; and facilitate formal verification as a means for determining whether complex systems designs adhere to functional, safety and security requirements.

All these key components will be integrated into the COLLABS Architectural Framework for Trustworthiness Assurance that enforces the rules to establish a comprehensive system for trustworthiness assurance.

Initial versions of all components in all three groups have been developed and made ready for presentation. Three components in Groups 2 and 3, Statistical Analytics and Machine- / Deep-Learning on Shared Data and Workflow-Driven Security for Supply Chain and Compliance in Manufacturing have also been successfully integrated into the first minimum viable product of the project. The two components in Group 1, Machine Learning-Based Cognitive Security Framework, have been created, initial functionalities realized, communication between them established and they have been initially tested. Demonstration of their operation is planned shortly after the first year of the project.

3. Security Component Descriptions

3.1 Machine Learning-Based Cognitive Security Framework)

The Machine learning-based cognitive security framework consists of two subcomponents, IoT secure wireless fingerprinting (Section 3.1.1) and ML S(N)C optimization and GMS tools (Section 3.1.2). The two components work together by the former component providing data (device fingerprints), and the latter producing machine-learning models capable of identifying devices and detecting anomalies. The envisioned interaction between the two subcomponents within the COLLABS framework is illustrated in Figure 1.

3.1.1 IoT Secure Wireless Fingerprinting

This component will provide inputs to the Machine learning-based cognitive security framework in the form of auxiliary information referred to as fingerprints, which are collected from wireless Industrial IoT devices and delivered along with the sensor data to the network server. Fingerprints represent all

information that can be acquired from an IIoT device which provides information about that device and its usual behaviour. Examples of fingerprint information include radio channel condition parameters, hardware-related imperfections attributable to a particular IIoT device, detailed energy consumption information, or similar. Based on the fingerprinting inputs, ML algorithms will be trained to differentiate between normal and abnormal identities of IIoT devices and initiate appropriate actions.

Functional Description

Depending on the wireless interface used by the IIoT device, this component will collect information about the radio-channel fingerprints from the device communication module and process this information into a useful stream of fingerprinting data. Use cases considered in the project will start with most common wireless IoT technologies such as IEEE 802.11ah or similar (Wi-Fi IoT) and 3GPP NB-IoT (Cellular IoT). For the emerging IEEE 802.11ah Wi-Fi IoT standard, we will use experimental platforms based on software-defined radios to generate and collect fingerprinting data. For IEEE 802.11ac standard, which is one of the commonly used broadband Wi-Fi interface used today, we will collect channel state information from commercial 802.11ac devices or access points. This imposes certain requirements, for example, in terms of the 802.11 chipset the device or access point is based on, as it is not possible to extract Channel State Information (CSI) as fingerprints for any available 802.11ac device¹. Finally, we will also collect fingerprinting data in the form of radio channel parameters (RSSI, RSRP, SNR) from 4G Cellular IoT devices based on 3GPP NB-IoT technology which is the main standard for 4G/5G cellular IoT connectivity.

¹ CSI is estimated at the lowermost physical layer of IEEE 802.11ac and this information is used to perform received signal equalization and correctly decode received data packets. However, this information is not forwarded to higher layers and standard commercial Wi-Fi device has no access to this information from Wi-Fi chipset. However, certain Wi-Fi chipsets (e.g., some Intel and some Atheros/Qualcomm chipsets) allow extraction of this information using appropriate drivers.

Figure 1 IoT wireless fingerprinting setup.

Preconditions and Input

Most of the commercially available IIoT devices are currently not suitable for the extraction of appropriate fingerprints from the device itself. The devices currently deployed at the use-case provider premises will most likely not be useful for demonstration purposes (although this remains to be confirmed). For this reason, development, and deployment of a new set of Wi-Fi/Cellular IoT devices suitable for fingerprinting collection will be required. This will be done first under lab conditions at UNSPMF premises, and then is planned to be transferred to a real-world deployment at use case providers.

Postconditions and Output

There are no specific postconditions. Once the IIoT device is capable of collecting fingerprints, it will send fingerprints formatted as other usually transmitted data from other onboard sensors, along this same data, in order to efficiently use communication opportunities. Thus, fingerprinting data can be considered as data coming from additional sensors.

Output of the component will be formatted in a way which is appropriate for interpretation by ML-based cognitive security framework. The data itself will most likely be delivered in the form of UDP packets and the UDP packet content may be formatted as deemed appropriate. For example, fingerprinting data may be delivered to the ML-based cognitive security framework as a feature vector representing average CSI values measured from the signals arriving at each of the Wi-Fi device/access point antennas and averaged across a sequence of a given number of last received Wi-Fi packets.

Component Design

Depending on the wireless interface, fingerprinting data can be collected in different ways. For Wi-Fi-based technologies, specific software tools are developed that need to be integrated within Wi-Fi access

points and/or Wi-Fi IoT devices in order to gain access to fingerprinting information². This will be first tested for the most common IEEE 802.11ac devices and access points for which there exists a solution for the extraction of CSI-based fingerprinting information (although not for every 802.11ac chipset). For IEEE 802.11ah, which is announced as the Wi-Fi standard for Industrial IoT, currently, there are no available devices on the market, although their appearance is expected soon. To alleviate this problem, we will use two types of devices, one is an experimental FPGA-based platform which is available at UNSPMF lab and is designed by one of the 802.11ah leading providers. As second device we use a Software-Defined Radio based platform which is capable of generating and receiving standard-compliant 802.11ah signals, which thus can be used for the purpose of fingerprint gathering (at least in the lab conditions and for the proof-of-concept purposes).

For 3GPP Cellular IoT devices, the device is already exchanging a lot of radio-interface parameters with the network, many of which could be captured at the IoT device and transmitted as auxiliary data back to the network servers and the ML S(N)C optimization and GMS tools component. We are also capable of designing and fabricating NB-IoT devices which could be customized for specific types of fingerprinting data collection. Our current NB-IoT testbed already possesses about 100 custom-designed NB-IoT devices which will be readily available for large-scale data collection purposes.

Addressed COLLABS Common Security Requirements

List of security requirements addressed by this component:

- CSR_01 - Identification and Authentication: This requirement is partially addressed by wireless fingerprinting component as it represents a crucial input for fingerprinting-based authentication and device identification.
- CSR_08 - Monitoring: This requirement is partially addressed by wireless fingerprinting as the input from wireless fingerprinting will serve as a data for IIoT device monitoring and anomaly detection.

Outlook

The initial version of the component will involve developing appropriate Wi-Fi and Cellular IIoT devices and collecting the corresponding data sets for training the ML-based cognitive security framework. The deployment and testing will be done exclusively at UNSPMF premises. In the further stages, the solutions for integration of both the IIoT devices and the ML S(N)C optimization and GMS tools component will be investigated in collaboration with the use case providers.

3.1.2 ML S(N)C Optimization and GMS Tools

The component is organized around a framework consisting of Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) models that enable the analysis of the behaviour of multiple IoT devices, as well as application to other COLLABS-related problems. For instance, data collected from the IoT secure wireless fingerprinting component will be fed into this component. The way input data (device signals) interacts with parts of the component, to produce the desired output and evaluation reports is illustrated in Figure 2.

² Currently, there are several tools available for integration with Wi-Fi devices. For example, Atheros CSI Tool (<https://wands.sg/research/wifi/AtherosCSI/>) can be used to extract this information from Atheros/Qualcomm-based chipsets.

Figure 2 IoT wireless fingerprinting setup.

Models can be built in a supervised or unsupervised way depending on the application domain and available data. If class labels are present (e.g., device IDs), supervised ML and DL methods can be trained to solve a classification problem (e.g., device identification based on various fingerprint features) or outlier detection problem (e.g., detecting faulty or compromised devices). If class labels are not present, unsupervised methods for outlier detection can be applied.

Functional Description

Modules of this component implement models for classification and anomaly detection (AD) that can be applied to fingerprint data, which include supervised methods based on support vector machines (SVMs), random forests, naive Bayes, and different architectures of deep neural networks, as well as unsupervised outlier detection methods. Models can be trained in a supervised or unsupervised way (depending on the availability of labels in collected data) to identify individual devices and/or detect anomalous device behaviour based on their fingerprints.

The functionality of the component is not limited to device fingerprinting, identification, and behaviour analysis; it can be adapted to any problem domain.

Preconditions and Input

- Preconditions: environment (native OS or VM) able to execute Python and associated libraries (scikit-learn, PyTorch, PyOD).
- Sufficient processing power and RAM for model training and deployment, depending on the problem at hand and employed data. GPU acceleration is recommended for training DL models.
- The component currently supports input of data in the form of .csv files; other means of input (e.g., direct network read) will be added as dictated by the project's needs.

Postconditions and Output

- There are no specific postconditions.
- The component currently supports output in the form of plain text and .csv files; other means of output will be added as dictated by the project's needs.

Component Design

The component consists of modules for:

- Data input and processing.
- Supervised machine learning (classification) by classical (non-DL) methods, including:
 - Support vector machines (SVM),
 - Naive Bayes,
 - Random forest.
- Supervised deep learning, including:
 - Fully connected neural networks (FNN),
 - Convolutional neural networks (CNN),
 - Recurrent neural networks (RNN), with different variants, including:
 - Long short-term memory networks (LSTM),
 - Gated recurrent unit (GRU).
- Unsupervised outlier/anomaly detection including methods based on:
 - One-class support vector machines (SVM),
 - Isolation forests,
 - Local outlier factor (LOF),
 - Angle-based outlier detection (ABOD),
 - k-nearest neighbours (kNN).
- Model evaluation:
 - Training/validation/test accuracy,
 - Training/test speed.

The component is written in Python and depends on external libraries scikit-learn, PyTorch and PyOD. Parallelization is supported by many methods.

Addressed COLLABS Common Security Requirements

- CSR_01 - Identification and Authentication: partially because the component introduces one of the means for device identification that can support classical methods for authentication and identification.
- CSR_08 - Monitoring: partially because the component provides one of the means for determining possible security breaches by detecting anomalous behaviour.
- CSR_10 - Integrity: partially because the component introduces one of the means for detection of equipment modification.

Outlook

The initial version of the component will be applied to the problems of device identification and threat detection in conjunction with the IoT Secure Wireless fingerprinting component. The deployment and testing will be done exclusively at UNSPMF premises. In the further stages, the solutions for integration of both the IIoT devices and the ML S(N)C optimization and GMS tools component will be investigated in

collaboration with the use case providers. In addition, the component will be used to address the task of Encrypted Traffic Analysis.

3.2 Statistical Analytics and Machine- / Deep-Learning on Shared Data

3.2.1 Security Infusion

This component is agent-based software which is used to monitor and secure any network's infrastructure. Security Infusion offers real-time and historical data access related to the collected, analysed, and visualised data concerning the security posture of a company. Security Infusion was designed based on ITML's experience of managing IT resources, and operational risk. The service's main aim is to do the job in a simple and efficient manner, without compromising the performance of the protected resource or accuracy of the data and information it collects regarding event and processes.

Functional Description

Security Infusion is a cloud-based, online service, mainly used for information security and event management of a network, which contains IDS functionalities as well. In the framework of the COLLABS pilots, the cloud might not be a valid option for some use cases, therefore edge deployment will be used as a substitute. In industrial environments, the component can be used to detect and mitigate threats on a multitude of vulnerable IoT Devices, by detecting unprecedented anomalies in an OT environment. Consequently, the platform creates alerts when a threat/anomaly is detected. It employs forensic analysis features which store information related to past logs and events, which administrators can access when needed. Security Infusion also delivers thorough vulnerability assessments and port scans to assess certain future issues and prepare administrators to avoid and/or resolve them.

Preconditions and Input

- The Infusion edge manager differs in preconditions depending on the number of agents:
 - For up to 20 agents, an AMD64 processor is needed, along with 2 CPUs and a 4G memory, where 75KB are needed per snapshot of the system.
 - For up to 100 agents, an AMD64 processor is needed, along with 2 CPUs and a 6G memory, where 75KB are needed per snapshot of the system.
- Consequently, the requirements differ depending on the OS type:
 - For the windows agent, a minimum of windows 7 OS, a 32/64bit, an intel i3-i5, and a 3G-4G memory are required.
 - For the Linux agent, a CentOS, or Ubuntu 18.04 OS, a 32/64bit, a JRE 1.8, an intel i3-i5, and a 3G-4G memory are required.
- Security infusion processes the following data:
 - Inputs system data, OS data and network data and syslog events,
 - Internet access to send data to the cloud is needed.

Postconditions and Output

- The output is mainly visual and can be saved in a Json format.
- Data processing occurs on minified / filtered data and events that the agents provide when installed.

Component Design

The service will consist of three sub-tools; the Infusion Agents, the Infusion Manager (Field gateway or Cloud based), and the Infusion Web Interface. The technologies comprising the submodules of Security Infusion are delivered via Kubernetes and Docker and are comprised by a plethora of toolsets/ frameworks like Laravel³ as the existing admin panel and dashboard, Java SDK⁴ for linux-based systems' agents, Nginx⁵ as a front end web layer delivering the cloud manager, and modules from the Elastic stack⁶ in order to persist data and be able to perform analysis on them.

The Infusion agents are basically responsible for data collection; therefore, they are deployed in the network. The agents can be deployed on Windows and Linux operating systems, which gives users the flexibility to use them wherever necessary. Consequently, there are two types of agents, the master agent is the one responsible for data streams, port scans, vulnerability assessments, and containing log servers, whereas the data agents explicitly collect data.

The Infusion manager is responsible for a multitude of operations including data reduction, threat management, and anomaly detection reasoner. Finally, security infusion contains a friendly UI, which contains the following features:

- Dashboard,
- Event Analyzer,
- Monitoring,
- Vulnerability and Port Scan,
- Reporting,
- Admin panel.

The aforementioned features, as well as the high-level functional diagram is shown in the following image.

Figure 3 The high-level functional diagram

³ Laravel PHP MVC framework, <https://laravel.com/>, accessed on December 2020

⁴ Java SE/EE SDK, Oracle, <https://www.oracle.com/java/technologies/javase-downloads.html> accessed on December 2020

⁵ Nginx web server, <https://www.nginx.com/>, accessed on December 2020

⁶ Elastic stack, <https://www.elastic.co/elastic-stack>, accessed on December 2020

Addressed COLLABS Common Security Requirements

- CSR-08 (Monitoring) fully because the agents collect and minimize this data and send it to the cloud manager.
- CSR-09 (Accountability and non-repudiation) Fully because the forensic analysis is covered by the module by storing data for a pre-defined period in order to allow post-event forensic analysis.
- CSR-15 (Availability) as long as it includes the cloud installation of the Security Infusion cloud manager.

Outlook

Security infusion will be providing the visualization components throughout the MVP use cases based on data collected for each use case’s environment. After attaining a sufficient amount of data, the tool will be further developed based on the end users’ requirements, which will be clearly defined after the first MVP is deployed. As elaborated earlier in the component design, a further in-depth development of the three Security Infusion sub-tools will be implemented, which includes a more sophisticated UI and the integration of an on-prem manager and upgraded agents for the selected use cases.

3.2.2 3ACES - Analytics as a Service

With the widespread use of big data analytics and its applications and the variety of data regarding size, type, and sources, industries are in a growing need of customisable tools which coincide with their changing requirements. Module Analytics as a Service (3ACES) is a tool which offers ideal decision support attributes for business through running big data analytics on whole datasets, regardless of the status which the datasets are delivered to the tool (structured, unstructured, or noisy). The data analytics features which 3ACES utilize depend heavily on machine learning algorithms which can serve in the clustering, classification, regression, and anomaly detection of the data presented.

Functional Description

The interface’s flexibility along with the tool’s applicability in a multitude of domains, makes it ideal to work in any business/ industrial environment with the help of its machine learning algorithms. The algorithms built in the system analyses the data in 4 main steps, as shown in the figure below:

Figure 4 3ACES data analytics process.

The Data Fusion Bus (DFB) sub-module of 3ACES can integrate several data sources related to a specified problem / use case. This data can then be analysed in a preliminary analysis using ML algorithms and assess the produced results (as defined/expected for each use case). Then several iterations with more data can enhance the accuracy of the results by further training the selected algorithm(s).

Preconditions and Input

- Onboard, the data steams as plain CSV files and/or as an Apache Kafka integration.
- MQTT events to be added within the scope of the project.

Postconditions and Output

- Provide output and respective feedback towards the end user or within the scope of the COLLABS framework to Security Infusion

Component Design

The analytics software applications created under the 3ACES framework are developed mostly as docker containers orchestrated by Kubernetes. This offers cloud optimization capabilities, allowing products based on the 3ACES framework to be deployed over public, private or hybrid cloud arrangements and enabling SaaS, and/or PaaS delivery models.

The tool also incorporates a set of ready-made open technologies, along with ITML's data fusion bus to produce a custom-made pervasive tool which both facilitates and supports businesses' decision-making processes. The open technology software includes:

- Apache Kafka data stream-processing software platform,
- KSQL streaming engine,
- Elasticsearch search engine and its stack (i.e., Logstash data streaming tool, Kibana visualization dashboard),
- Apache Spark - for programming data processing patterns, mostly using Python,
- Apache zookeeper coordination service,
- Grafana metric analytics & visualization suite,
- Laravel web programming environment.

The data fusion bus (DFB) enables the system to synchronize data from heterogeneous sources, while also providing data distribution and common data sharing interfaces to third-party services.

Addressed COLLABS Common Security Requirements

- CSR_08 (Monitoring) fully because providing the service containerized allows for OOTB monitoring tools targeted to cloud-based installations.
- CSR_14 (Availability) fully due to the backup of the cloud-native nature of the tool that allows for regular backups that ensure the protection against data loss.
- CSR_04 (Authorization), CSR_10(Integrity), and CSR_11(Integrity) all fully because all logs and data are maintained in an environment such that access is granted to specific users on a least privilege principle.

Outlook

3ACES' main role will be realized following the deployment of the first MVP in most use cases to accommodate data integration between modules (per use case or for the whole COLLABS framework), giving the chance to the tool to be further developed employing the data it collects through the first pilot. Succinctly, the overall customization of 3ACES which will be used in the final MVP will also be realized as the requirements become more apparent post-deployment and testing.

3.3 Workflow-Driven Security for Supply Chain and Compliance in Manufacturing

3.3.1 Workflow-Driven Security Framework (WDSF)

The workflow-driven security framework (abbrev. WDSF) is a framework (Kasinathan & Cuellar, 2019) that is used to model and implement complex business processes, making use of a distributed ledger architecture for concise audit log and to enable workflow-aware access control across organizational boundaries. That way, WDSF allows digitizing distributed business processes and enforcing their compliant execution. In COLLABS, WDSF is used to model collaborative manufacturing and remote maintenance use cases. In such scenarios, stakeholders of different organizations - such as manufacturers, suppliers, or service providers - collaborate and, thus, must establish and manage trust across organizations. WDSF addresses these requirements by providing transparency and accountability (non-repudiation) of workflow steps execution through a shared (distributed) immutable ledger.

Functional Description

WDSF is a security framework that is used to:

- Model, specify, simulate, validate, and verify the digital representation of business processes (i.e., modelled as one or more workflows).
- Enforce correct executions of distributed business processes, denoting the adherence to the defined steps of processes and compliance with pre- and post-conditions.
- Guarantee workflow integrity, traceability, and accountability of actions.

WDSF includes a manual modelling phase and a semi-automated deployment and execution phase as illustrated in Figure 5, below. First, via a sequence of 4 interactive modelling steps, the workflow is designed and implemented using Petri Nets - these 4 steps are done manually:

- (1) In the first step, the business process needs to be defined and the interaction between the stakeholders needs to be clarified. In the example of a remote maintenance scenario, this phase involves representatives of the manufacturing company (such as shop floor manager and enterprise IT manager) as well as service providers (e.g., key account manager of the maintenance company).
- (2) Based on the initial stakeholder's input, the process activity is modelled via user friendly activity diagrams. Usually, one of the stakeholders involved creates the activity diagram.
- (3) The activity diagrams get reviewed by all the stakeholders involved in the first step and approved.
- (4) Next, a Petri Nets based workflow is modelled representing the business process activity diagram. This step also includes simulation, validation, and verification of Petri Nets workflow properties

such as deadlock freeness and soundness. After successful validation, the Petri Nets can be directly executed via the workflow application.

The deployment and workflow execution are shown in the second half of Figure 5 where the workflow gets implemented via the following steps.

- (5) Based on the Petri Nets workflow, smart contracts⁷ are created. Thereby, the basic structure of smart contracts can be automatically generated (Zupan, 2020). This approach reduces both the effort for smart contract development and interpretation errors while implementing the business process specified in the first step. Specific semantics, like the evaluation of preconditions represented in a custom data structures are use case specific and cannot be automatically generated so that this step is performed semi-automatically. Note: The Petri Nets workflow may contain additional workflow steps that need not be represented in the deployment of the smart contracts.
- (6) In the next step, the smart contracts are deployed on the distributed ledger, e.g., in Hyperledger Fabric each organization (stakeholders) should accept the smart contract before it becomes functional. The architectural layers, including the blockchain, are described in more detail in the next sub-section.
- (7) Finally, the workflow can be executed. Based on the Petri Nets based workflow model and implementation, compliance with the business process is enforced. Parallel workflow execution is supported via the eventual consistency provided by the underlying blockchain for synchronizing the workflow events across multiple actors in different organizations.

Steps (5) to (7) are executed semi-automatically using WDSF. Please note that all steps are shown in consecutive order. In case of changes in the business process or if any rectifications are needed, previous steps will be re-executed. These iterations have been omitted in the figure for the sake of brevity.

Figure 5 WDSF process steps.

After having performed the steps as illustrated in Figure 5, a digital implementation of a business process is provided. The business process' workflow is implemented via a Petri Nets based workflow engine as will be described in the architecture section below. The business logic - i.e., the validation of preconditions and the implementation of postconditions of a step in the process - is realized via the Petri

⁷ Smart contracts are executable programs. These are used to control, document or automatically execute actions (can also be legally relevant events), according to the terms of a contract that stakeholders have agreed upon. See, for instance, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Smart_contract and <https://hyperledger-fabric.readthedocs.io/en/latest/smartcontract/smartcontract.html#>

Nets workflow engine. The Petri nets workflow engine may interact with smart contracts when a workflow step's action and the corresponding information (i.e., input and output data that needs to be maintained as part of an audit log) gets stored in the underlying blockchain for auditability purposes. The blockchain can be setup as a distributed network with different stakeholders (such as manufacturers and maintenance companies) having access to it.

Preconditions and Input

WDSF uses REST APIs for interacting with external applications, such as IIoT devices or services and Web-based applications. WDSF exposes a Web application interface (GUI) for workflow execution. Workflow steps and their validations are use-case specific. Hence, input parameters and metadata must be evaluated as preconditions of transitions. In the context of COLLABS these input parameters could be access tokens (e.g., JSON Web Tokens, JWTs) representing access permissions to perform a certain step in the process. Input tokens can be evaluated by two different components in the WDSF architecture: a) via the Petri Nets workflow engine; b) via smart contracts deployed in the blockchain. Depending on the use case specific conditions, validation can be done in either one or in both components.

For a workflow to be executed via the workflow engine, WDSF uses an upload interface. Petri Nets are used for modelling and specifying workflows. WDSF expects workflow definitions using PNML (Petri Nets Markup Language, which is specified via ISO/IEC15909-2⁸) as standardized import/export format.

Postconditions and Output

The Petri Nets-based workflow engine transforms states of the workflow based on input provided by actors into new states with workflow-specific post-conditions. That is, after executing a transition in the workflow, well-defined states in the Petri Nets are reached. In addition, the transition can also generate tokens as output that represents postconditions. In the context of COLLABS, output tokens can be simple assertions of a state, or access tokens to access next resources (e.g., JSON Web Tokens, JWTs). Generation of output tokens can be implemented in two different components in the WDSF architecture: a) by the Petri Nets workflow engine; b) via an external authorization or IAM component deployed together with WDSF. It depends on the trust of the Workflow execution application. That is, if the workflow execution engine and its application are trusted and they run in a tamper-proof environment, then the workflow execution application can itself generate access tokens; otherwise, it is recommended to use a state-of-the-art authorization server to generate access tokens. In this case the workflow application needs to establish a secure connection with the authorization server.

Component Design

Figure 6 provides a high-level overview of the system architecture of the Workflow-driven Security Framework (WDSF).

⁸ <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso-iec:15909:-2:ed-1:v1:en>

Figure 6 WDSF system architecture.

The system components are:

<p>User Interface</p>	<p>We assume that web portals (e.g., for an approval process in the context of a remote maintenance access process) are provided for human users to interact with the business process, e.g., to pick up tasks and approve certain steps.</p> <p>Web UIs are not in scope of the WDSF development as such, as they are use case specific. Because of that portals as well as the interaction with external IT applications like identity and access management system (IAM) will also not be in scope of further technical evaluation.</p>
<p>Workflow Application</p>	<p>The user interface layer is interacting with the WDSF workflow application. This represents the middleware that is implementing the application logic. The WDSF workflow application makes use of a Petri Nets-based representation and implementation of the overall business process. The Petri Nets-model defines the steps and transitions of a business process, i.e., the workflow.</p>
<p>Smart Contracts</p>	<p>Smart contracts represent the second layer in the WDSF architecture where the application logic is implemented. While the (Petri Nets-based) WDSF workflow application is enforcing the workflow execution and workflow compliance, Smart Contracts are for instance used to perform semantic checks, like validation of tokens and signatures to check that the approval of a request has been performed by an authorised user. Furthermore, the smart contracts layer also acts as a policy enforcement point (PEP), evaluating whether a requestor/user is able to perform a certain step in the workflow. Such checks are implemented via so-called smart contracts on top of the blockchain layer.</p>

Blockchain Platform	<p>A blockchain infrastructure is used to store any transaction, i.e., any activity in the workflow. The benefits of using blockchain technology are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immutability of information stored in the blockchain. That is, the blockchain infrastructure is used as a reliable, distributed audit log that ensures non-repudiation of actions. • Authenticity of actions, meaning that the originator of an action can be identified and authenticated. Please note: the main requirement is to be able to identify the origin of actions. That applies to many industrial use cases. Therefore, anonymity - which represents another key feature of a blockchain infrastructure - is not used, by intent. • Decentralization denotes the possibility to distribute information across the nodes of different stakeholders. This depends on the deployment scheme used for the blockchain infrastructure. • Transparency, meaning the possibility to distribute information across participating nodes so that all authorized parties can get access to shared information.
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In that sense, the overall system architecture (as illustrated in Figure 6) follows a three-tier design with the UI being realised in form of web portals, the application layer being realised through (a) the Petri Nets-backed WDSF workflow application and (b) smart contracts, and the data layer in form of the distributed ledger/blockchain.

The benefit of separating the application into (a) and (b) is that we can use the best out of both technology stacks, meaning that the Petri Nets-based WDSF workflow application focuses on enforcing the workflow/business process (i.e., execution paths) while additional conditions are checked (=pre-conditions) and created (=post-conditions) by smart contracts that have direct access to information stored in the blockchain or off-chain.

The implementation of WDSF is based on the following technology stacks/3rd party libraries:

- For the web portals (for demonstration purposes) we make use of use case specific web applications that were developed using the FLASK⁹ framework.

The WDSF workflow engine is realized using SNAKES¹⁰ which is a Python library used to define and execute Petri Nets-based workflows. In that sense, the overall system architecture (as illustrated in Figure 6) follows a three-tier design with the UI being realised in form of web portals, the application layer being realised through (a) the Petri Nets-backed WDSF workflow application and (b) smart contracts, and the data layer in form of the distributed ledger/blockchain.

The benefit of separating the application into (a) and (b) is that we can use the best out of both technology stacks, meaning that the Petri Nets-based WDSF workflow application focuses on enforcing the workflow/business process (i.e., execution paths) while additional conditions are checked (=pre-conditions) and created (=post-conditions) by smart contracts that have direct access to information stored in the blockchain or off-chain.

⁹ FLASK - <https://palletsprojects.com/p/flask/>

¹⁰ SNAKES - <https://snakes.ibisc.univ-evry.fr/>

The implementation of WDSF is based on the following technology stacks/3rd party libraries:

- For the web portals (for demonstration purposes) we make use of use case specific web applications that were developed using the FLASK¹¹ framework.
- The WDSF workflow engine is realized using SNAKES¹² which is a Python library used to define and execute Petri Nets-based workflows.
- As underlying distributed ledger architecture, we make use of Hyperledger Fabric¹³ with smart contracts implemented in JavaScript.

Addressed COLLABS Common Security Requirements

Via the integration of WDSF in COLLABS' use cases, the following requirements as identified in D1.2 will be addressed:

- CSR-03 Authorization (timed access)
 - WDSF will evaluate the context of requests (e.g., via checking access control tokens including expiration dates), thus granting access for the least required time, only
- CSR-04 Authorization (least privilege)
 - WDSF is used to implement the business process of remote maintenance in a controlled and restrictive way, denoting that the least-required access path for a remote service engineer will be realized, only.
- CSR-07 Logging
 - WDSF's architecture includes a distributed ledger technology (e.g., Hyperledger Fabric) which is used to log each important interaction of the workflow participant (e.g., maintenance person, devices, etc), ensuring integrity and availability of log data.
- CSR-09 Accountability and non-repudiation
 - Accountability and non-repudiation are fulfilled by WDSF through the underlying blockchain architecture as each interaction is logged by ensuring authenticity (using digital signatures)

Outlook

For the realization of the MVP, WDSF will be used for designing and implementing distributed, collaborative workflows like the remote maintenance scenario (ALES scenario S1 "Controlled and secure remote maintenance", see D1.2). The MVP will focus on compliance enforcement of distributed workflows. After the MVP we will focus on extending the interfaces of WDSF as well as connecting to external components (e.g., firewalls) via invoking their control interfaces.

4. Methods for Screening and Improving the Security of Future COLLABS Solutions

4.1 Methods and Guidelines for Oblivious Machine Learning

4.1.1 Advanced Cryptography Tools

¹¹ FLASK - <https://palletsprojects.com/p/flask/>

¹² SNAKES - <https://snakes.ibisc.univ-evry.fr/>

¹³ Hyperledger Fabric - <https://www.hyperledger.org/>

In Task 2.1, we leverage powerful cryptographic tools (homomorphic encryption, secure multiparty computation) to protect the ML and DL algorithms. As described in D1.4, in COLLABS a DL outsourcing scenario will be adopted, as a locally running DL model will be migrated to the Cloud. The main security goal is to protect the confidentiality of both the input data and/or the model.

ALES is working on the refinement of P&W Scenario #2 (from Deliverable D1.2) to define the requirements for the application of HE. In particular, ALES is considering the case where a compliance dataset and analysis algorithm are deployed on the cloud for product compliance analysis (images, geometrical measures, sensor data).

Given our use case scenario, we have decided to protect the model execution with Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) as the FHE schemes have limited communication overhead compared to SMC ones which are very interactive. The main DL operations that will be implemented are:

1. Convolution
2. Matrix multiplication
3. Activation functions: ReLu.
4. (Max) Pooling

Since 2009, the performance of FHE computations has impressively improved with a speedup of 10^9 . However, programming FHE applications remains a demanding task that requires cryptographic expertise (*R. Cammarota, 2020*). The non-expert programmer can use the multiple available implementations (there are several open-source libraries), but as has been reported, the produced code can be 10^3 times slower than the code written by an FHE expert.

In Task 2.1, we provide recommendations and guidelines on the optimal usage of the available schemes. Emphasis will be given to the ML and DL models used in COLLABS. The main goal is to optimize the trade-offs between security, performance and accuracy and facilitate the programmer in managing the encryption parameters, the noise level, and the data approximation.

4.1.2 Writing a FHE Program

The initial program (plaintext program) can be re-written as a FHE program by naively replacing all the computations with the corresponding FHE ones (mainly additions and multiplications). However, this approach does not scale and can be extremely slow (more than 10^3 times).

The general structure of a FHE circuit appears in the following Figure 7.

Figure 7 The FHE circuit structure.

All the proposed FHE schemes can compute any program. However, in order to achieve that, they need a rekeying operation called bootstrapping (orange circles in the scheme). This operation is very costly and the FHE programmers must avoid it if possible. The boxes between the bootstrapping operations are called Levelled HE (LHE) circuits. This part implements a circuit with a given multiplicative depth L .

That is that - the programmer with a LHE can implement any plaintext program with multiplicative depth up to L . However, the larger the value of L , the slower the program becomes. Thus, the programmer must find the optimal combination of the values L_1 , L_2 , etc., such that the overall complexity is the minimum possible. Such optimization is still an open problem and strongly relies on experience.

In what follows, we provide guidelines and recommendations for the unexperienced programmer to create an efficient FHE program. Emphasis will be given to the implementation of efficient LHE programs. The programmer needs to make several decisions, including the selection of scheme, the specific data layout (for parallelism) and the encryption parameters, among others. The LHE program must be secure, efficient, and correct.

4.1.3 Selection of the FHE Scheme

While the first FHE schemes only supported Boolean operations (resulting to rather huge circuits), the last generation of FHE designs are able to homomorphically perform integer operations. This allows us to evaluate arbitrary arithmetic circuits efficiently without having to “explode” them into Boolean circuits. Among them, the most efficient ones are BFV, BGV and CKKS. All of them are constructed on the Ring Learning with Errors (RLWE) problem.

Practical applications, like the DL model inference, require floating point arithmetic and approximate computation. However, all the FHE schemes support only integer operations. Thus, in order to obviously compute using these schemes, we use fixed-point arithmetic and we explicitly define a scaling factor. While we can use all three FHE schemes with fixed-point arithmetic representation, only CKKS (and its variant RNS-CKKS) can give practical programs. The problem is the fast increase of the scaling factor with multiplication. In order to cope with that, we need to select huge encryption parameters, and especially an extremely large plaintext-coefficient.

However, CKKS offers another alternative, as it enables ciphertext rescaling. It allows the programmer to reduce the scaling factor, at the expense of less accuracy. Actually, this is exactly the paradigm of floating-point arithmetic. We are going to use CKKS in COLLABS.

All three FHE schemes support four main evaluation operations:

1. addition of ciphertexts,
2. addition of ciphertext and plaintext,
3. multiplication of ciphertexts and
4. multiplication of ciphertext and plaintext.

The FHE schemes implement nicely polynomial computations. For applications that use non-polynomial operations (like \exp , \log , etc.), it is assumed that such functions can be approximated by polynomials. It has been demonstrated that this is possible for ML and DL.

Another important parameter is batching compatibility. In order to compute in parallel operations on messages, data can be processed in SIMD (single instruction multiple data) like way that allows a vector of input messages to be encoded in a single plaintext. With batching, the operations take place in an element-wise fashion increasing efficiency. All three FHE are batching compatible.

4.1.4 FHE Libraries

There are several open-source libraries that implement the three main schemes. In Table 1, we provide the main ones. We want to emphasize that the field is very dynamic. Theoretical advances and new improved implementations change the scenery rapidly.

<i>Library</i>	<i>HE schemes</i>
<i>MS SEAL</i>	<i>BFV (RNS), CKKS (RNS)</i>
<i>HELib</i>	<i>BGV, CKKS</i>
<i>Palisade</i>	<i>BGV, BFV, CKKS</i>
<i>HEAAN</i>	<i>CKKS</i>

Table 1 FHE open-source libraries.

CKKS is the most suitable scheme for ML and DL applications and there are two versions of the scheme. The first is referred to as plain “CKKS,” while the second is known as “RNS-CKKS.” Both have open-source implementations, like the HEAAN, PALISADE¹⁴ and SEAL libraries. We will mainly use the last one, as it offers more efficient implementations that can use machine-sized integer operations as opposed to multi-precision libraries. However, it imposes further restrictions on the circuit multiplicative depth. Thus, we will have to decide on a per use case.

4.1.5 FHE Security

Each FHE is initialized with a set of parameters. The value of these parameters determines the level of security, the efficiency, and the accuracy of the scheme. In COLLABS, we will first decide on the security level, and then we choose the other parameters. The level of security will be at least 128 bits (security parameter).

For the same level of security, the encryption parameters affect the performance and the accuracy of the generated FHE program. Typically, larger values lead to more accuracy, but slower programs, while smaller values to faster and less accurate programs. Choosing an adequate set of parameters is tricky.

Current FHE schemes work by introducing noise during encryption that is subsequently removed during decryption. The amount of noise introduced during encryption and every intermediate operation is controlled by a set of encryption parameters that are set manually. Setting these parameters low can make the encryption insecure. On the other hand, setting them large can increase the size of encrypted text and increase the cost of homomorphic operations. Moreover, when the accumulated noise exceeds a bound determined by these parameters, the encrypted result becomes corrupt and unrecoverable.

The parameters must be chosen following the recommendations of the “HomomorphicEncryption.org,” the open consortium of industry, government, and academia for the standardization of homomorphic

¹⁴ <https://palisade-crypto.org>

encryption. Following the white paper¹⁵ (section 5.4) that they maintain, the parameters must be chosen following the tables provided.

4.1.6 FHE Correctness

In all FHE schemes, noise is added in every homomorphic operation, and this noise must be controlled in order to perform correct decoding at the end. The CKKS scheme introduces an additional challenge by providing approximate results (of course with much higher efficiency). There are two extra sources of error: the error from the initial encoding of the input values and the noise from the rescale operation.

FHE Error

All the evaluation operations increase the level of noise. The level of noise must be controlled and always remain under a certain bound for correct computation. There are two main approaches. Either we increase the level of tolerance, i.e., the acceptable upper bound of noise, by increasing the ciphertext coefficient, or we reduce the level of the produced noise periodically during the computations. More precisely:

- The upper bound of acceptable noise depends on parameter Q , the ciphertext modulus. This parameter can be increased to afford noise increase, but at the expense of reduced efficiency.
- The programmer can apply a modulus **switching operation**. This operation reduces the level of noise by modifying the ciphertext modulus. The modulus is divided by one of its factors. However, the modulus switching operation can only be applied a limited (predefined) number of times and it is a costly operation.
- Limit the number of multiplications. The ciphertext multiplication operation increases the level of the noise exponentially. Thus, it is necessary to choose computations that minimize the multiplication depth of the circuit to be evaluated.
- Use bootstrapping to reset noise. This operation re-encrypts the ciphertext homomorphically and it is a very expensive operation.

Selecting the Scaling Factor

Neural network models typically use floating-point values that must be transformed to fixed point and determining the optimal fixed-point scaling factors to use is not straightforward. The use of fixed-point arithmetic with scaling factors introduces two problems:

1. The encoding can be lossy.
2. The scaling factor increases very fast with multiplications,

Determining the scaling factors to use for the inputs and the output is difficult as it involves a trade-off between performance and output precision. This is **an open problem**.

Using high enough scaling factors allows errors to be hidden. However, the computations become shortly expensive as the scaling factor increases. Furthermore, power functions computation would rapidly overflow modest values of the modulus Q , requiring impractically large encryption parameters to be selected. In order to control the size of the scaling factor, CKKS supports an operation called rescaling.

Rescaling operation

¹⁵ http://homomorphicencryption.org/white_papers/security_homomorphic_encryption_white_paper.pdf

CKKS schemes support an operation called rescaling that scales down the fixed-point representation of a ciphertext. Practically, it truncates the fixed-point representation. Consider a ciphertext x that contains the encoding of 0.25 multiplied by the scale 2^{20} , the rescaling operation will truncate to encode the value at a scale of 2^{10} .

Rescaling has a secondary effect of also dividing the ciphertext's modulus Q by the same divisor as the ciphertext itself. That means that there is a limited "budget" for rescaling built into the initial value of Q . This is similar to the modulus switch operation. However, the modulus switch does not affect the scale factor, only it brings down the level of a ciphertext.

Regarding the RNS-variants of CKKS that is supported by SEAL, the truncation is performed by dividing the encrypted values by prime factors of Q (it is the product of r distinct prime integers). The order of the prime factors is fixed, i.e., the order of the divisions is fixed. That means that from any point there is only one valid divisor available for rescaling. The value of Q is reduced by this factor each time.

The rescale must also be lower bounded with respect to the output. If the output scale is less than a value, the computed output probably loses accuracy, and this is irreversible. This complicates selecting points to rescale, as doing so too early might make the fixed-point representation so small that the approximation errors destroy the message. The user decides on the input and output scale. Also, the maximum allowed rescale factor can be defined. In some implementations this maximum value is dictated by the library, like in the SEAL library (2^{60}).

Input encryption coefficients correctness

To apply any homomorphic operation, the two input ciphertexts must be at the same level, i.e., must have the same modulus Q . Furthermore, all additions (and subtractions) require that the input ciphertexts are encoded at the same fixed-point scale. A homomorphic evaluation is correct, when:

- **Rule 1 (addition):** Two ciphertexts that are added must have the same modulus coefficient and the same fixed-point scale factor.
- **Rule 2 (multiplication):** Two ciphertexts that are multiplied must have the same modulus coefficient (not the same fixed-point scale factor, necessarily).

CKKS also supports a modulus switching operation. The application of the modulus switching operation modifies the current modulus Q and brings down the level of a ciphertext without scaling the message. Inserting the appropriate rescaling and modulus switching operations to match levels and scales is a **non-trivial task**.

Relinearisation

A ciphertext is initially represented by two polynomials. However, the multiplication of two ciphertexts (consisting of several polynomials each) yields the ciphertext of the result with more computations than the initial ones (if q and w are the input, then $q+w+1$ polynomial will be the result). To set a bound on the number of polynomials an expensive operation, called relinearisation, is performed. Relinearisation reduces the number of polynomials to the input value (i.e., $q+w$) and using a distinct public key.

Selecting the optimal placement of relinearisation operations is proven to be an **NP-hard problem**. Usually, relinearisation takes place after every multiplication so that a ciphertext needs always only two polynomials to be represented. However, it is an open problem to find other (better) strategies, given that the decryption operation can be generalized easily to the m -polynomials representation, with $m > 2$.

4.1.7 FHE Efficient Implementation

The cost of individual homomorphic operations are orders of magnitude more expensive than the equivalent plaintext operations. Thus, we must compute them in parallel as much as possible. At the same time there is another weapon in our arsenal, the so-called batching.

Batching

Amortising the cost of FHE operations requires utilizing the vectorization capabilities (also called as “batching” in the FHE literature) of the FHE schemes. Data can be processed in a SIMD-like way by encoding a vector of input messages in a single plaintext. With batching, the FHE operations take place in an element-wise fashion increasing efficiency. The SIMD width in CKKS and RNS-CKKS is $N/2$ and they support rotation operations that mimic the shuffle instructions of the SIMD units. The rotation by i requires a different public key for each i . We usually produce keys for all the powers of 2 (until N). Also, they do not support random access to get a particular slot value from the ciphertext. We need a multiplication with a plaintext for such operations.

However, vectorization is **not a straightforward procedure**. Different mapping on to ciphertext vectors results in different circuits with different performances. More precisely, for each resulting circuit the programmer must determine the encryption parameters that maximize performance while ensuring security and correctness. We will propose cost-based guidelines to assist the programmer in systematically searching over the different options.

4.1.8 Guidelines and Recommendations

We provide general guidelines for the programmers based on the analysis above. It is still necessary to have a good understanding of HE and its limitations. First, we provide guidelines for an implementation that does not use ‘batching.’ We recommend an unexperienced programmer to get familiar with such designs. Then, we provide guidelines regarding message vectorization.

‘Simple’ Approach for LHE Circuit Design

- ✓ Choose the appropriate FHE scheme. We assume that CKKS will be the selection for DL inference.
- ✓ Select the version of plaintext circuit with the minimum multiplicative depth
- ✓ Select the input and output level of accuracy.
- ✓ Select the maximum rescale factor (in SEAL this must be 2^{60}).
- ✓ Replace all the operations (additions and multiplications) with the corresponding FHE ones.
- ✓ Use relinearisation after each FHE multiplication.
- ✓ Use rescale, if needed, after each multiplication.
- ✓ Verify that the input data of all operations has the correct input encryption coefficients. Place the modulus switching operation where necessary.
- ✓ Compute the value of the modulus coefficient Q . Q is either power of 2 or the product of r prime numbers. We want to minimize either $\log Q$ or number r .
- ✓ Use the table of coefficients to get the minimum possible value N .
- ✓ Estimate the performance of the circuit using asymptotic complexity (Table 2). Be careful that we can get only a rough estimation as the hidden coefficients have a massive impact. Always it is better to measure the complexity of the actual implementation.

<i>HE Operation</i>	<i>CKKS</i>	<i>RNS-CKKS</i>
addition, subtraction	$O(N \cdot \log Q)$	$O(N \cdot r)$
scalar multiplication	$O(N \cdot \log Q)$	$O(N \cdot r)$
plaintext multiplication	$O(N \cdot \log N \cdot M(Q))$	$O(N \cdot r)$
ciphertext multiplication	$O(N \cdot \log N \cdot M(Q))$	$O(N \cdot \log N \cdot r^2)$
ciphertext rotation	$O(N \cdot \log N \cdot M(Q))$	$O(N \cdot \log N \cdot r^2)$

Table 2 Asymptotic complexity of the main CKKS HE operations. $M(Q)$ is the complexity of multiplying large integers¹⁶.

- ✓ Implement all the operations at the same level in parallel.
- ✓ Free memory when possible.

Vectorized Approach

LHE efficiency can be significantly improved using batching. The ‘Simple’ LHE must be rewritten and all data must be organized in vectors. Such an implementation is suitable for neural network inference, where all operations are tensor operations. The programmer must first design the vectorized version of the tensor circuit and then apply the guidelines described above.

Note: Batching can be applied in simple LHE as well without any modification. It covers the case that we have several input data for prediction.

For the vectorized circuit:

- ✓ The rotation operation needs a different public key for each l -position cyclic shift of the message.
- ✓ The SIMD width in all CKKS versions is $N/2$. That is that - we can store up to $N/2$ messages in a plaintext.
- ✓ The mask operation increases multiplicative depth.
- ✓ There is a trade-off between splitting a large tensor and increasing N to fit it in.
- ✓ There are several choices of layouts. I.e., several different ways to store the messages in a plaintext slot (rewrite input as a vector).
- ✓ Depending on the data layout, different operations must be applied. The best layout selection depends on the complexity of each operation per FHE scheme.

¹⁶ CHET: an optimizing compiler for fully-homomorphic neural-network inferencing. R Dathathri et al. Proceedings of the 40th ACM SIGPLAN Conference on Programming Language Design and Implementation. 2019

Addressed COLLABS Common Security Requirements

- CSR_08: Confidentiality.
 - FHE encryption protects the confidentiality of data input and the DL model (when needed). As FHE schemes are based on the Learning with Errors problem (LWE), they also offer postquantum protection.

Outlook

This is not a component. We mainly introduce techniques and guidelines for the transformation of DL (or ML in general) models into oblivious ones. The proposed tools will be used for the protection of the product compliance analysis algorithm for Scenario 2 of ALES. ALES is working with P&W manufacturing site for the definition of the data content/format, type of analysis algorithm, toolchain, and integration constraints and, it is doing an investigation of open-source technologies for integration of an oblivious variant of the compliance analysis algorithm for COLLABS demonstration purposes.

4.2 Distributed Anomaly Detection for Industrial IoT

4.2.1 Overview / Functional Description

Industrial Control Systems (ICS) are systems that are part of Operational Technologies (OT). Their functions are management, monitoring and control of infrastructure and industrial processes. This applies to manufacturing plants, industrial plants, electrical power and energy systems and other critical infrastructures. In the past, these systems were not intended to be accessible remotely. They remained in closed and controlled environments and were isolated from corporate networks and external networks. Thus, protocols used by such systems implemented little or no security features. Lately, in order to improve their efficiency, the ICSs integrated communications technologies from the world of Information Technology (IT). They are also more and more open and connected to services on corporate networks or on external networks. This openness brings great flexibility and benefit in the management of industrial processes. It also enables the development of new high added-value functions for industrial infrastructures. On the other hand, it exposes these infrastructures to new attack surfaces, such as cyber-attacks that were specific to IT technologies. Especially since legacy ICS protocols were not developed to deal with these attacks.

Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) are applications that monitor a network or system in order to detect attacks and malicious behaviour that takes place there. In particular, Network Intrusion Detection Systems (NIDS) are IDSs used to monitor networks.

A NIDS collects network traces and analyses them to detect attacks or intrusions into the monitored network. The NIDS performs Deep Packet Inspection (DPI), and extracts information about the upper layers of the OSI models in the packet capture. This analysis can have low latency constraints. In these cases, the performance of NIDS is particularly important as it must analyse large amounts of information and return information in a very short time. In some cases, these time constraints can be relaxed, and more extensive processing can be performed.

Different intrusion detection techniques exist. The signature-based methods of attacks use a knowledge base of existing and already listed attacks. These methods recognize the characteristics of the known attacks in the analysed network packets. Signature-based methods require access to a set of attack signatures. With such methods, it is not possible to detect an attack that is not listed in the set of signatures.

There are also anomaly-based intrusion detection methods. These methods aim to detect abnormal behaviour or communications between network components. They often use machine learning algorithms to determine the normal behaviour of the network. It is then possible to detect deviations from this normal behaviour in the network. Anomaly-based IDSs may detect zero-day and unknown attacks.

ICSs have specificities such that the usual IT security measures cannot be applied systematically:

- There are often constraints about response time between devices, which make it difficult to use cryptography mechanisms to ensure data integrity and/or confidentiality.
- These time constraints may also disallow using simple filtering equipment, as it may introduce too much latency.
- Protocols used in ICSs such as Modbus or DNP3 are not secured by design, and a corrupted node inside the network may not be detected. It may produce illegitimate frames in order to disrupt the functioning of the ICS.
- As ICSs operate continuously, they are not updated frequently. Often, updating such a system is done at scheduled maintenance operation, where it is shut down. Consequently, if a vulnerability on a device is referenced, it will not be corrected until the next scheduled maintenance. During this time, the ICS remains vulnerable.
- An ICS has a lifespan of several decades. Even if the future ICSs are integrating more and more cybersecurity primitives, the current and legacy systems do not necessarily have these possibilities. They are therefore exposed to vulnerabilities.

Regarding this context, IDSs are suitable for ICSs. IDSs allow enhancing the security and attacks detection on industrial systems without interfering with their operation.

There are different metrics to assess the relevance of an IDS. The most common ones are:

- the maximum throughput that the IDS can support,
- the false alarms rate,
- the detection rate,
- the coverage, which is the set of attacks that are detectable by the IDS,
- the robustness against evasion techniques and attacks directed at the IDS.

It is possible to categorize different attack types on ICS networks, depending on the scope of their targets and their applications:

- Network wide attacks are attacks targeting (or originated from) a large number of devices on the network. These attacks can evade device-wise analysis systems. For instance, a Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attack with low traffic generation per device may not be detected by a device-wise attack detection system. It may be necessary to look at network traffic statistics to detect these attacks.
- Single target attacks are attacks targeting a single device on the network. These attacks can fool statistical analysis systems since it can be stealthy. For instance, scanning open ports on a single target on a network with lots of devices and communication may not be detected by statistical analysis. It is necessary to look at a per-device traffic to detect these attacks.

Attacks on the network are characterized by malicious packets. These packets divert or intend to divert devices from their nominal operations. It is possible to categorize different malicious packet types:

- Data Maliciousness packets are packets that hold malicious data that intent to exploit some vulnerability at the target. For instance, command injection, malware uploading... belong to this malicious packet type. These packets may hold the malicious data at the application layer and thus may need special analysis of their transport layer's payload.
- Contextual Maliciousness packets are packets that are not malicious by themselves, but they are sent for malicious intention. For instance, flooding attacks and replay attacks use legitimate packets to disrupt the operation of the network. These packets can normally be seen in both benign and attack scenarios. The context they come in decides whether they are malicious or not.

Challenges of Distributed Anomaly Detection (Model Detection)

The application of IDS technologies to ICSs encounters several challenges. Indeed, ICSs use heterogeneous, and sometimes proprietary, communication protocols. As a result, many of these protocols are not supported by conventional IDSs. The use of encryption in application layers limits the packet analysis capabilities of IDSs.

The limited communication resources of some devices of the ICSs, their spatial distribution as well as the latency requirements of industrial processes make the collection of network traces complicated. This may result in the need to deploy multiple network probes to capture traffic. Since each probe has a capture of local exchanges, it will not have a global view of ICS communications.

ICSs systems are driven by industrial process constraints. Their communication characteristics are predictable and relatively constant. The anomaly-based methods for IDS are therefore privileged for these systems. These approaches tend to generate a high rate of false positives. Training machine learning models can also be complicated by a low volume of communication, resulting in insufficient training data.

Distributed Learning

Most distributed learning algorithms have their foundations in ensemble learning. Ensemble learning builds a set of classifiers in order to enhance the accuracy of a single classifier. Although there are other methods, the most common one builds the set of classifiers by training each one on different subsets of data. Afterwards, the classifiers are combined in a concrete way defined by the ensemble algorithm. Thus, the ensemble approach is almost directly applicable to a distributed environment since a classifier can be trained at each site, using the subset of data stored in it, and then the classifiers can be eventually aggregated using ensemble strategies. In this sense, the following are the advantages of distributed learning:

- Using different learning processes to train several classifiers from distributed data sets increases the possibility of achieving higher accuracy, especially on a large-size domain. This is because the integration of such classifiers can represent an integration of different learning biases which possibly compensate one another for their inefficient characteristics.
- Learning in a distributed manner provides a natural solution for large-scale learning where algorithm complexity and memory limitation are always the main obstacles. If several computers or a multi-core processor are available, then they can work on a different partition of data in order to independently derive a classifier. Therefore, the memory requirements as well as the execution time, assuming some minor communication overhead, become smaller since the computational cost of training several classifiers on subsets of data is lower than training one classifier on the whole data set.

- Distributed learning is inherently scalable since the growing amount of data may be offset by increasing the number of computers or processors.
- Finally, distributed learning overcomes the problems of centralized storage. Thus, many research works on distributed data learning have been concentrated on ensemble learning where the emphasis is put on making accurate predictions based on multiple models.

4.2.2 Architecture Design: High Level

In this section, we describe our distributed anomaly detection system.

Level-3 security requirements for the COLLABS framework include monitoring various data flows from IIoT devices using cognitive security mechanisms like model-based verification and machine and deep learning for detection of anomalies. Moreover, COLLABS focuses on AI-based solutions for the edge and analysis of encrypted network flows.

Trade-off between accuracy and performance will be further improved using Reservoir Computing in combination with deep learning methods with a wide range of available resources from edge to the cloud. Another requirement is related to encrypted traffic analysis mechanisms based on metadata extraction that will use machine and deep learning techniques. For wireless IoT devices, these methods will be applied to datasets acquired from wireless fingerprinting.

The system is composed of local components that are deployed on the edge of the network (Figure 8). We call these components "Local Detection Units" (LDU). Each LDU is assigned a role to analyse and detect anomalies in network traffic locally.

Figure 8 Distributed Anomaly Detection System.

As a black box, an LDU takes as input the raw network traces of the monitored network. Depending on the deployment scenario, the LDU can be connected to a span port that provides network traffic with (almost) no latency (Figure 8). The LDU produces decisions regarding the analysed packets. In addition, LDUs communicate with each other to share information that aims to increase the accuracy of detection.

In detail, an LDU is composed of multiple machine learning (ML) models. Each of the ML models analyses different features in the analysed packet. These models start with pre-trained parameters and are updated over time using the previously monitored traffic. A **Pre-processor** component first parses the packets and extracts relevant features. The **Activator** then activates the corresponding ML model depending on the type of treated features. Each activated ML model outputs the decision and the confidence level. Finally, the **Accumulator** merges the output of the activated ML models, based on predefined rules, into a final decision. Since the models are updated, updates on the local models' parameters need to be transferred to other LDUs. Sharing these updates increases the efficiency of the learning process. We leverage distributed learning to share these model updates.

Figure 9 Local Detection Unit.

Our system manages efficiently the overhead of distributing the learning information. A Distributed Learning Service (DLS) runs on each LDU. A DLS regularly transfers and receives learning information from and to the LDU ML models.

Pre-Processing

Network traffic is mirrored toward the LDU as raw packets. The Pre-processor first extracts identification information from the packets. This information is used to choose which models are activated for this packet. The identification information may be:

- Source MAC address,
- Destination MAC address,
- TCP session,
- Application Layer Protocol.

The **Pre-processor** then parses these packets and extracts the relevant features from them. As a preliminary step to build an accurate and precise IDS, it is important to understand the potential attacks on the system. Attacks can be split into network-wide attacks and single-target attacks. Also, packets can be malicious in different ways: data maliciousness packets, and contextual maliciousness packets.

Driven by the fact that the first step to detect an anomaly is to look at the right place, and since knowing "where to look" is equally important to knowing "how to look", the step of feature extraction from raw packets is a critical step for an efficient IDS. However, not all these attacks can be revealed from the same features. Hence, we propose to categorize the types of extracted features into three categories: Packet statistical features, Packet's metadata features, and Packet's payload features. We categorize

features in this fashion since each of these categories reveals information relevant about special types of attacks.

Parsing Packet Statistical Features

These features are statistical data collected over a window of N packets. They may include:

- Transmission rate,
- Reception rate,
- Packet size mean,
- Packet size standard deviation,
- Ratio of TCP packets,
- Ratio of UDP packets.

By analysing these features, we are able to detect network-wide attacks.

Parsing Packet Metadata Features

These features are extracted mostly from the headers of the Network and Transport layers. They may include:

- Source port,
- Destination port,
- Packet length,
- TCP Flags: SYN | SYNACK | ACK | PUSH | FIN,
- Protocol: TCP / UDP / Other.

By analysing these features, we are able to detect single-device attacks, especially the ones that are attained using contextual malicious packets.

Processing Packet's Payload Features

These features are extracted from the payload of the transport layer. Since this is highly dependent on the application protocol used, the pre-processor extracts the payload and handles it as raw data. Later, the respective ML model parses this raw data depending on the identified application. A mechanism for analysing encrypted network traffic might be used. It will rely on the metadata that can be found inside packet headers, including packet lengths, timestamps, direction, and inter-arrival times. By analysing these features, attacks using data malicious packets can be detected.

Activator

The Activator transfers features extracted from a packet to a specific ML model. We follow a methodology of fine-grained separation of models and creating conditions for their activation and for the features they analyse. Therefore, the Activator is designed to register handlers for each ML model deployed in the LDU. The handler contains:

- The method to call that ML model,
- The inputs of the callable ML model,
- The conditions when this model is called.

When a model is deployed, these three pieces of information need to be specified for that model. For example, model M_x can be deployed and registered such that it takes as inputs all the statistical features

and is called on packets originating from devices that are of type D_x . Activator can also take into account the resource consumption of the LDU and the volume of network traces to process before deploying or not ML models.

Machine Learning (ML) Models

The ML models are the core of the system. Each ML model works independently to detect certain anomalies in an analysed packet. It runs on specific packet features passed by the Activator. It then outputs a value between 0 and 1 representing the probability of the analysed packet being anomalous. The ML models are treated as black boxes, so there are no constraints about their internal design. An example of ML models can be Recursive Neural Network (RNN) models, Deep Neural Network (DNN) models, Support Vector Machine (SVM) models, etc. Models can be added or removed from the system at any time to adapt to computing resources, to changes in the network topology, on the latency requirements and on the security requirements. To design our system, we think that three types of models are needed to detect all types of attacks mentioned in Section 4.2.1.

General Models: MG

- **Description:** Analyse the overall behaviour of the devices to detect network-wide attacks such as worms.
- **Input Features:** Packet statistical features from N consecutive packets.
- **Training Data:** All network packets.
- **Activation Conditions:** On receiving N packets.
- **Possible Designs:** Clustering (SVM, k-means), Outlier Detection (Local Outlier Factor, Isolation Forest).

Devices Specific models: MD x

- **Description:** Analyse the behaviour of a specific device on the network to detect an anomaly in the device performance with respect to the normal behaviour of devices of the same type. Thus, a model per device type is trained and a copy of the trained model is spawned for each device in the network.
- **Input Features:** Packet's metadata features.
- **Training Data:** Packets received and sent by devices of the same type of device x .
- **Activation Conditions:** On receiving packets from/to the device x .
- **Possible Designs:** RNN (Gated Recursive Units, Long Short-Term Memory), Auto-Encoders.

Application Specific Models: MA x

- **Description:** Analyse the payload data on the application layer to detect anomalies in the device's behaviour with respect to normal data used by the device's application. A model per application protocol is trained and a copy of the trained model is be spanned for each opened session.
- **Input Features:** Packet's payload features.
- **Training Data:** All the payload data for application app sent/received by all devices such app is the protocol used in session x .
- **Activation Conditions:** On receiving a packet belonging to session x .
- **Possible Designs:** NLP techniques (BERT, Transformers, RNN).

Accumulator

When a packet is mirrored to the LDU for analysis, multiple models can be activated. The Accumulator is the component that merges the output of the different activated models and gives as a result the final decision about the analysed packet. The Accumulator can be a decision tree whose parameters are trained in a supervised manner. In this case, the decision tree can be trained using real world attack scenarios.

Distributed Learning Service (DLS)

Distributed learning seems essential in order to provide solutions for learning from both “very large” data sets (largescale learning) and naturally distributed data sets. It provides a scalable learning solution since the growing volume of data may be offset by increasing the number of learning sites. Moreover, distributed learning avoids the necessity of gathering data into a single workstation for central processing.

Distributed clustering or effective voting are two strategies that can be adopted for distributed machine learning. They also can be used alone or in combination with other algorithms such as decision rules, stacked generalization, meta-learning, knowledge probing, distributed pasting votes, effective stacking, or distributed boosting,

Despite the clear advantages of distributed learning, new problems arise when dealing with distributed learning as, for example, the influence on accuracy of the heterogeneity of data among the partitions or the need to preserve privacy of data among partitions.

Addressed COLLABS Common Security Requirements

Regarding security requirements, CSR_08 is partially covered because our system provides a mean to detect anomalous behavior. Moreover, *our distributed anomaly detection system will be not part of MVP. It will be more detailed and refined in the next deliverables D2.2 and D2.3.*

4.3 Formal Specs Verifier (FSV)

Formal Specs Verifier (FSV) is an industrial-strength formal verification framework, providing an environment for analysis of complex systems designs against functional, safety and security requirements. The framework is structured into: (1) a translation layer, supporting automated and formal transformation from a system design language to a mathematical model including formal requirements specifications, (2) an algorithmic layer, where the various verification objectives are addressed by specific verification algorithms, (3) an analytic layer, where computational tasks generated by verification conditions are discharged by backend engines, such as SAT/SMT/OMT solvers, industrial and academic model checking tools, internally developed analytics for specific verification tasks. The platform has a high-maturity core, developed across the years, and is currently adopted in multiple industrial programs, and it can be extended with more explorative/research tools/analyses by leveraging its layered architecture. Extensions can include design and specification languages, new verification tasks and related algorithms, novel analysis back-ends.

Functional Description

The FSV framework has been used in several industrial and research projects, and extensions have been presented for the verification of embedded systems (*Ferrante, Benvenuti, Mangeruca, Sofronis, & Ferrari, 2012*), synthesis of failure scenarios (*Marazza, Ferrante, & Ferrari, 2014*), automatic test

generation (Ferrante, Marazza, & Ferrari, *Formal Specs Verifier ATG: a Tool for Model-based Generation of High Coverage Test Suites*, 2016), requirements validation (Mangeruca, Ferrante, & Ferrari, 2013) as well as applications to concrete industrial size cases.

In the context of COLLABS the main functionalities exposed by FSV are:

- Property verification: given a model with properties described as invariant or temporal logic formulae the tool can apply different formal techniques with the aim of verifying (proving) the property or falsifying it providing a counterexample
- Synthesis of failure scenario: given a model, the specifications of failure modes that can affect any component in the model and a set of properties that should hold regardless the system failures the algorithm provides a Minimal Critical Failures Set (MCFS) that leads to an unsafe behaviour (invalidated property).

Preconditions and Input

FSV takes as input Simulink/Stateflow models. Therefore this is a strong precondition for its usage. Furthermore, models and the properties must be specified according to specific modelling guidelines to be fully supported by the tool. These modelling guidelines guarantee that FSV will properly preserve the semantics of the source model during translation into the target language suitable for model checking.

Postconditions and Output

The expected output of the tool is different based on the features used:

- Property verification: the assessment of a design can end with three different results. If the property is invalidated, the tool returns a counterexample that (simulated) allows to reproduce the behaviour invalidating the property. Instead, if the property gets proven the tool returns confirmation of its validity. The third possible outcome can be “unknown” which is the case if the engine cannot solve the problem (e.g., bounded model checking, or timeout reached).
- Synthesis of failure scenario: this assessment can end with three different results. A minimal set of failures that can lead the system in an unsafe state (if the property is invalidated), or a confirmation of soundness if the property is proven to be valid even under fault conditions. The third possible outcome can be “unknown” which is the case if the engine cannot solve the problem (e.g., bounded model checking, or timeout reached).

Component Design

FSV works on formal models designed in Simulink and Stateflow following proper design guidelines. The toolchain consists of four main components:

- Parser: in this phase the input is processed by using a MATLAB API-based parser that reproduces the model using an internal formal intermediate representation. During this phase, the tool detects unsupported blocks or unsafe constructs, if present.
- Model translator: the internal representation is processed and optimized with the objective of producing a formal model that encodes the input model as a finite state machine. In addition, (1) a set of assumptions on the primary input of the system (Environment model) and (2) the property to be verified are translated and processed by the optimization phase as specification patterns.
- Target language encoder: finally, this step produces artifacts that can be processed by state-of-the-art model checking tools such as NuSMV.

- **Formal analyser:** FSV is capable to interface different verification engines. The main used is NuSMV which is a symbolic model checker used for the verification of industrial designs.

Figure 10 Formal Specs Verifier transformation flow.

Addressed COLLABS Common Security Requirements

FSV will not be deployed as part of the COLLABS framework therefore it is not directly addressing any of the Common Security Requirement (CSR) identified in D1.2.

This tool is a support utility that will be used to formally prove at design level that the solutions proposed by COLLABS are addressing properly the security requirements by verifying at design level that the required security properties satisfy the CSR.

Outlook

The development of the tool is out of COLLABS scope, in the context of this project we will just apply formal techniques exploiting FSV capabilities.

5. An Architectural Framework for Trustworthiness Assurance

5.1 Trust Infrastructure Overview

To ensure trustworthiness of data flows in collaborative manufacturing environments, COLLABS will design and develop components composing the trust infrastructure, presenting an architectural framework for trustworthiness assurance. Said framework will encompass:

- The provisioning of secure elements (see subsection 5.2.1) that will make use of built-in secure hardware to form a root of trust and verify the integrity of the code running in the device.
- The security of data in transit, via:
 - An encrypted data flow model based on which data from IoT devices will be able to be securely transferred and processed in trusted execution devices or end cloud-services, covering all upstream and downstream data flows, and supporting an extensive toolkit of cryptographic primitives, including SMC and Homomorphic encryption.
 - A novel mechanism to analyse encrypted traffic analysis (see subsection 5.2.3) that will further strengthen the data flows trustworthiness by capturing attacks or anomalies

inside the real network traffic of the platform and reporting them to the anomaly detection modules.

- The security of data at rest, providing privacy-preserving mechanisms for the storage and analytics, based on Comprehensive Access Control mechanisms, supported by blockchain to achieve a distributed authentication scheme (see subsection 5.2.2).

An overview of the above-mentioned key elements comprising the COLLABS Architectural Framework for Trustworthiness Assurance is presented in Figure 11 below. The figure also provides references to the specific Tasks (both within WP2 and within WP3 and WP4) where the individual building blocks will be developed. It also aims to provide a visual representation of the interplay between these activities and the associated components.

Figure 11 The COLLABS Trust Infrastructure high-level architecture.

5.2 Key Building Blocks

The subsections that follow provide an overview of the key features of each of the framework’s key building blocks, including - where needed - pointers to specific deliverables where more details can be found.

5.2.1 Secure Elements

Figure 12 Secure Elements' enablers.

At the lower level of the trust architecture, COLLABS integrates trust enablers at the hardware level, leveraging the presence of trusted components on the platforms to be deployed in the manufacturing environment. These are detailed in the subsections that follow.

Trusted Execution Environments

In order to account for the increased requirements for securing a number of primitives and computations in an expanding interconnected “world” of systems, modern processors of all levels and complexities have started to integrate Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs). In server and cloud environments where high-performance devices, commonly Intel x86-64 architecture-based CPUs are used, the most prevalent TEE technology is Intel SGX. In the embedded computing space, dominated by low-power devices, ARM architecture is the most widely used and the ARM TrustZone extensions are used in order to build a Trusted Execution Environment.

The Intel SGX technology can be used to protect selected code and data from disclosure or modification. It is an ideal solution for untrusted environments, such as commodity cloud environments in which the user has minor control over aspects like the storage of the data. SGX can guarantee privacy even with an untrusted service provider.

At its root, Intel SGX is a set of CPU instructions that can be used by applications to set aside private regions of code and data. They allow user-level as well as operating system code to define private regions of memory, called enclaves, whose contents are protected and unable to be either read or saved by any process outside the enclave itself, including processes running at higher privilege levels.

SGX involves encryption by the CPU of a portion of memory. The enclave is decrypted on the fly only within the CPU itself, and even then, only for code and data running from within the enclave itself. The processor thus protects the code from being “spied on” or examined by other code. The code and data in the enclave utilize a threat model in which the enclave is trusted but no process outside it can be trusted (including the operating system itself and any hypervisor), and therefore all of these are treated as potentially hostile. The enclave contents are unable to be read by any code outside the enclave, other than in its encrypted form.

In the context of COLLABS, SGX-protected docker images can be setup in the cloud. Inside the docker images, sensitive applications may be executed, and those applications can be protected by external entities which may share the server or datacentre infrastructure of the cloud provider that hosts them.

On the other side, for IoT or edge devices based on ARM processors the TrustZone technology can be leveraged in order to secure computations and the protection of sensitive data, such as encryption keys. TrustZone is built on the foundation that the security of a system is achieved by partitioning all the system’s hardware and software resources in two worlds: The Secure World for the security subsystem and the Normal World for everything else. At the hardware level, TrustZone-enabled devices include

logic that ensures that no Secure world resources can be accessed by the Normal World components while architecture extensions in the ARM cores allow the concurrent execution (in a time-sliced fashion) of Normal and Secure World applications.

Typically, in the Normal world resides a Rich OS, like Android or Linux, along with different applications and services. In the Secure world, a much more restricted secure operating system that provides a Trusted Execution Environment is executed. In the context of COLLABS, one of the TEEs that is considered is Trusty, a free and open-source TEE operating system, part of the Android Open-Source Project (AOSP).

Trusty boots as part of a chain of trust or a secure boot sequence. It creates two environments in a device with different security modes: A Non-Secure Environment (NSE) for running software components in non-secure mode (i.e., the aforementioned Normal world) and a Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) that provides trusted operations and runs in secure mode enforced by hardware (Secure world). Trusty runs in the Secure world environment. The normal world OS and Trusty software operate in a client-server relationship, with Trusty as the server. All secure operations are initiated by a client application running in the non-secure environment. A trusted application (TA), in the secure world, never initiates contact with the non-secure environment.

A Trusted Application is defined as a collection of binary files (executables and resource files), a binary manifest, and a cryptographic signature. At runtime, Trusted applications run as isolated processes in unprivileged mode under the Trusty kernel. Each process runs in its own virtual memory sandbox utilizing the memory management unit capabilities of the TEE processor.

Remote Attestation

Remote attestation is one of two security mechanisms that threat protection, prevention, and monitoring functions in the COLLABS framework rely on. It is a security mechanism that provides evidence of device reliability - a protocol that allows proving software integrity to a remote verifier, which provides evidence that the software has not been modified. This is achieved by signing protected memory areas.

For instance, in a situation when potential attackers have physical access to an IoT device, they may attempt to tamper with device firmware and try to attack it and plant some malicious code that could pose a threat for privacy and security of the entire COLLABS framework. Remote attestation offers a solution to prevent such attacks by remotely checking the integrity of the IoT device's firmware, comparing it to the known original and offering guarantees for its integrity.

Challenges that need to be addressed before remote attestation can be included in the COLLABS framework include:

- the question of current remote authentication schemes not considering the interaction between devices, and
- the question of scalability in case of usage of many devices and applying remote authentication schemes without compromising system performance.

5.2.2 Data Protection

Data Protection enablers within the COLLABS trust infrastructure, as developed within WP2, will consider both data in transit and data at rest. These will be supported by the distributed authentication & authorisation mechanisms developed in the context of WP3. These enablers and their interplay are depicted in Figure 13.

Figure 13 Data protection enablers.

Encrypted Data Flow Model

An integral part of the COLLABS trust infrastructure is the definition of an encrypted data flow model that specifies the use of cryptographic primitives available within COLLABS, based on which data from IoT devices will be able to be securely transferred and processed in trusted execution devices or end cloud-services.

The model encompasses standard encryption mechanisms and best practices (e.g., for end-to-end encryption over public networks) but also innovative primitives developed within COLLABS (e.g., SMC and Homomorphic encryption).

An overarching aim of the specification of the data flow model is to consider and protect all upstream and downstream data flows (device to gateway, gateway to cloud, C&C channel). In this context, and in order to consider all such flows and the intricacies of each Use Case environment, a detailed analysis of the UCs, their scenarios, and the associated requirements (as defined within D1.2 and D1.3) was carried out, followed by consultation with UC owners (namely ALES, PCL, and REN). Through this process, the key flows needed to support each UC and its associated scenarios were identified and are depicted in Figure 14. Said figure and the derivatives that will be presented in the subsections that follow, also include the Purdue model layers, for reference and to maintain homogeneity with the descriptions provided in D1.2 and D1.3. If a scenario is omitted, it means that no data flows are specified for that scenario at this stage.

Figure 14 Overview of key data flows in Use Case scenarios.

The data flows are shown in terms of the Purdue Enterprise Reference Architecture levels, as well as the corresponding layers of each of the UC environments, classified per scenario (see label within arrows), and characterised in terms of the need to support standard or homomorphic cryptographic primitives.

Following this high-level specification of the data flows, a more detailed specification must be provided for each of the UC environments and the corresponding scenarios. To this end, an analysis of available options (e.g., Information Flow diagrams, Data Flow diagrams) in the context of the COLLABS needs was

carried out and the use of Information Flow diagrams was selected as the most appropriate means of defining said model, as it provides the needed level of granularity and the means to specify cryptographic primitives and their settings/configuration to protect data flows, without requiring a high level of specificity for the applications that may be supported from the specific data flows.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that the Data Flow Model will be a “live” component, constantly being updated and refined as: (a) the COLLABS solution matures from a technical perspective, and (b) the UC environments and associated scenarios are specified in more detail, paving the way for the onsite COLLABS deployment and real-life demonstration (see WP6). Therefore, as the project matures and the model evolves, the appropriateness and limitations of the Information Flow-based specification will be constantly assessed and, if the need arises, the Data Flow Model may be transferred to a different format, e.g., in a more application-specific or even machine-processable format, (through the definition of the associated grammar).

The subsections that follow provide more details on the Data Flow Model specification for the different UCs and associated scenarios.

ALES Industrial Environment

Four scenarios are identified within the ALES industrial environment that feature data flows with strong security requirements. These are highlighted in the subsections that follow.

ALES Scenario 1 - Controlled and secure remote maintenance

This scenario focuses on remote equipment maintenance from external/third party services, with support from local staff. The external/third-party services access the network and equipment, with temporary authorisations and strong segregation with respect to existing functions and data. More details on the

scenario are provided in D1.2 (Section 2.b.ii.1). The data flow model for this scenario is shown in

Figure 15 ALES Scenario 1 (Controlled and secure remote maintenance) data flow model.

Figure 15 ALES Scenario 1 (Controlled and secure remote maintenance) data flow model.

ALES Scenario 2 - Controlled share of compliance data

Compliance data is collected from the manufacturing process and is used to evaluate and testify on the quality of manufactured goods. This compliance check may be carried out by cloud-based quality check services. In such instances, design data shall be granted to not be leaked to other ongoing computations and, whenever possible, it would be preferable to guarantee data encryption while at rest and under analysis to avoid loss of intellectual property or technical data. More details on the scenario are provided in D1.2 (Section 2.b.ii.2). The data flow model for this scenario, also leveraging homomorphic encryption during compliance checks, is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16 ALES Scenario 2 (Controlled share of compliance data) data flow model.

ALES Scenario 3 - Trusted compliance data share across the supply chain

The manufacturing of complex and safety-critical systems requires collaboration between supply chain parties. Automation of these complex information flows requires to establish trust, guarantee integrity, support traceability and accountability, potentially without relying on a single central authority. Typically, a customer requests a batch of parts with quality/compliance information attached, and the enterprise receives this request, dispatching the production order to the manufacturing zone. During production, the shop floor sends process data to the data integrator, while the set of information about the product and its supplies shared with the customer through the internet. More details on the scenario are provided in D1.2 (Section 2.b.ii.3). The data flow model for this scenario is shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17 ALES Scenario 3 (Trusted compliance data share across the supply chain) data flow model.

ALES Scenario 4 - Analysis of manufacturing performance on a global scale

In this scenario process data is collected from the shop floor and used for performance analysis and optimization at the Enterprise layer, closing the feedback loop onto the local factory. This is also extended across multiple factories, allowing for improvement of inventory/stock and the ability to reconfigure production according to market needs. Therefore, sanitised process data is also shared with the global performance monitor through the internet. More details on the scenario are provided in D1.2 (Section 2.b.ii.4). The data flow model for this scenario is shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18 ALES Scenario 4 (Analysis of manufacturing performance on a global scale) data flow model.

PCL Industrial Environment

Two scenarios are identified within the PCL industrial environment that rely on specific data flows with intrinsic security requirements. These are highlighted in the subsections that follow.

PCL Scenario 1 - Shop floor threat detection and prevention

This scenario focuses on the shop floor and its connection with the factory infrastructure. Networking in a shop floor environment is not managed by PCL due to organizational and political reasons. This lack of insight introduces a significant level of risk and therefore a security appliance is introduced between the shop floor and manufacturing zone. In COLLABS this appliance is expected to be a "Prevention Tool", and all communications to/from the factory floor will go through this tool, while it will be responsible for encryption, authenticity and integrity of the data received from the shop floor and send it to the manufacturing network. More details on the scenario are provided in D1.2 (Section 2.a.ii.1). The data flow model for this scenario is shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19 PCL Scenario 1 (Shop floor threat detection and prevention) data flow model.

PCL Scenario 2 - Remote data sharing

This scenario revolves on remote data sharing (i.e., sharing with external/third parties) for collaboration purposes. Interactions with equipment and tool suppliers to develop new manufacturing processes, and collaboration with consortium partners in European, national as well as regional innovation projects, require a secure data exchange solution, for confidential and business critical data. Said solution must be flexible, work bidirectionally, and be able to deal with all sorts of (near real-time) machine and process data. More details on the scenario are provided in D1.2 (Section 2.a.ii.2). The data flow model for this scenario is shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20 PCL Scenario 2 (Remote data sharing) data flow model.

REN Industrial Environment

Three scenarios are identified within the REN industrial environment that rely on specific data flows with intrinsic security requirements. These are highlighted in the subsections that follow.

REN Scenario 1 - Controlled and secured remote maintenance

Maintenance operations, setting up production chains, and supervision of industrial processes shall be executed remotely. For this, remote access to all levels of the Purdue model is required. Nevertheless, this remote access must guarantee a strong segregation with respect to existing functions and data, and especially ensure the integrity and availability of the critical production process. It should also guarantee the confidentiality of the data in the production environment, as the maintenance operations must be realized without revealing any sensitive data. More details on the scenario are provided in D1.2 (Section 2.c.ii.1). The data flow model for this scenario is shown in Figure 21.

Figure 21 REN Scenario 1 (Controlled and secured remote maintenance) data flow model.

REN Scenario 2 - Cloud-based architecture for industrial processes

This scenario is motivated by the cloud-based smart factory of Industry 4.0 paradigm, modifying the production process to adopt a cloud-based agent approach to create an intelligent, collaborative, and more flexible industrial environment. Various partial use cases can be derived in this regard, as resources and services are progressively hosted externally in private/public cloud providers. An integral challenge is the need to collect more and more data from the manufacturing process, which are generated and collected for different domains of the industrial process regarding maintenance, performance, production, quality, and compliance. They key areas of impact are the shop floor level, as well as the manufacturing and enterprise zones. More details on the scenario are provided in D1.2 (Section 2.c.ii.2). The data flow model for this scenario is shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22 REN Scenario 2 (Cloud-based architecture for industrial processes) data flow model.

REN Scenario 4 - Security of connected devices

The objective of this scenario is to increase the security of the industrial environment providing security to low-cost IoT (sensors, actuators, etc.) and industrial automation devices. To achieve this, it is essential to identify the hardware security components, the cryptographic mechanisms, and the protocols pertinent to each device, while respecting their resource constraints and intricacies. Of importance is the usability of the chosen mechanisms, the provision of an effective convergence between OT and IT, with adapted protocols, and the adoption of distributed, collaborative protocols with mutual authentication mechanisms between devices to allow for automated segmentation based on devices security policies, and the security management of the devices throughout their lifecycle. More details on the scenario are provided in D1.2 (Section 2.c.ii.4). The data flow model for this scenario is shown in Figure 23.

Figure 23 REN Scenario 4 (Security of connected devices) data flow model.

SMC & Homomorphic Encryption

One of the tasks of the COLLABS framework is to leverage powerful cryptographic tools, like homomorphic encryption and secure multiparty computation, to protect ML and DL algorithms and their input data’s confidentiality. Data will be protected at any time as they will always remain encrypted. However, mapping complex functions onto advanced cryptographic techniques remains an ad hoc process and practically always requires cryptographic expertise to be done correctly and efficiently.

In the context of COLLABS, we provide guidelines and recommendations for hand-crafting DL solutions with advanced cryptographic techniques aiming to facilitate the work of the non-expert programmer. The AI models introduced in the COLLABS scenarios will be transformed into trustworthy AI inference systems demonstrating the effectiveness of the proposed optimizations. More details can be found in subsection 5.1.1.

Privacy-preserving Storage & Analytics

One of the tasks of the COLLABS framework is to offer privacy preserving data storage and analytics, while observing the need for easy integration and input of heterogeneous data and facilitating the adoption of collaborative analytics to enterprises. The solutions developed within the project allow - even in the MVP version of the framework - different participants to jointly process sensitive data without

disclosing sensitive and confidential data to anyone outside and ensuring compliance with data access and privacy criteria.

Reliable statistical methods and machine and deep learning methods are defined and will be made available to different parties in the production chain in a privacy-preserving way. This is particularly aimed at the context of machine and deep learning where the service provider can have a model that returns predictions on the input data, and the user can get those predictions on their data without the need to expose sensitive information. This process will be further improved by applying differential privacy-based methods on shared data. With differential privacy appropriately defined, privacy guarantees are achieved by the introduction of randomness, by the data provider, in response to queries, which machine and deep learning algorithms are sent to the database. Amount of noise added to the original information is controlled by the so-called epsilon factor or privacy cost that represents a trade-off between the level of privacy achieved and the performance of a machine or deep learning algorithm. Such implementation of machine and deep learning algorithms will make it possible to configure trade-offs in terms of privacy and performance according to the needs of data owners.

Distributed Authentication & Authorisation

In a complex system such as the COLLABS framework, authentication and authorisation cannot be centralised since that would by its nature represent a security risk. Distributed authentication and authorization are achieved through a comprehensive mechanism involving various approaches including distributed PKIs, blockchain, device fingerprinting, attribute-based access control, etc. The following two subsection will overview the comprehensive access control mechanisms employed in COLLABS, as well as blockchain and smart contracts.

Comprehensive Access Control

Comprehensive access control is a data protection mechanism of the COLLABS framework. It includes security services based on trust for IoT authentication and ensures communication between trusted components only.

Communication between cloud-based applications within the COLLABS framework is managed and protected using identity and context-based access control. We use a distributed PKI mechanism to authenticate users and devices removing the need to use passwords and using certificates instead of them. Using blockchain to manage certificates will prevent tampering and ensure consistency of certificates, raising security one more level up.

On another level, the COLLABS framework contains fingerprint methods for IoT devices that may be used to detect abnormal behaviour and abnormal signals received from edge devices. We use advanced machine learning and deep learning methods to analyse the data acquired by IoT device fingerprinting to detect outliers and anomalous behaviour. Such a mechanism provides an additional level of security and confidence in industrial scenarios.

Access rules are managed centrally, at the point of policy decision-making. Using attribute-based access control (ABAC) will allow precise and flexible definition of access rules using the XACML standard. IoT devices have low processing power and low memory capacity which makes them unsuitable to act as servers. In that case, attribute-based encryption (ABE) can be used to ensure trust between the sensor and the end user. That way the IoT device only needs to encrypt the data it sends, and the policy decision point will send the decryption key to the end user. In this way, it is ensured that communication adheres to the described rules described.

Blockchain and Smart Contracts

A **distributed** ledger implements a decentralized record of transactions. A **blockchain**¹⁷ is a particular type of distributed ledger. A **ledger** is the sequenced, tamper-resistant record of all transitions approved on the blockchain. It is a growing list of cryptographically linked records (blocks). Each block contains a **cryptographic hash** of the previous block, a timestamp, and transaction data. The blockchain is designed to resist the modification of its data. Once recorded, the data in any given block cannot be altered without needing to alter all subsequent blocks. A blockchain is usually managed by a **peer-to-peer** network where peers follow a common inter-node communication and block-validation **consensus protocol**. A **peer** is an individual participant of a blockchain network. Generally, each peer holds a copy of the ledger, which can be modified only when the majority of peers agree on it via their **consensus protocol**.

There are **public** (permissionless) blockchains, and permissioned (private) blockchains. **Permissioned** block-chains need a way to identify the participants of the network, like an identity and access management (IAM). Peers can only read and propagate transactions they are entitled to. There are different distributed ledger **platforms**, like Ethereum, Corda, and Hyperledger Fabric¹⁸ (HLF). In permissioned block-chains like HLF the consensus protocol can be changed and adapted to fit specific use cases via policies. For instance, you can restrict which nodes need to verify the transactions and which nodes do not, and you can use consensus protocols that do not require costly mining.

We value distributed ledger technologies for their cryptographically granted security properties, like **immutability** and **accountability** (non-repudiation). Parties, even if they do **not trust each other**, can collaborate **without** the need for **trusted third parties**. A blockchain allows untrusted parties to collaborate under a strict and formal agreement for assurance. Distributed ledger technologies often (like when no party controls more than 50% of the nodes) can ensure the following properties:

Immutability means that once a transaction is stored on the ledger it cannot be deleted or modified any longer. **Transparency** is given as peers must accept all interactions with the ledger, they can observe and confirm each transaction and only validated transactions are written to the blockchain. An immutable and transparent ledger allows for **auditability**. For **accountability** (non-repudiation), an IAM system identifies participants in the ledger network and allows tracking their actions. In case one needs to resolve a dispute, the accountable party can be traced.

Each peer node contains a copy of the distributed ledger. Peer-to-peer data sharing guarantees **redundancy** of the database and allows checks for **consistency**. Due to this redundancy, failure of one node does not affect the **availability** of the remaining system. **High availability** may be achieved. A blockchain represents a distributed system with the potential for supporting high Byzantine fault tolerance. Due to peer consensus of the transactions, the system can be regarded as **reliable** and **fail-safe**, even if some peers default.

Blockchains offer a decentralized, immutable, and verifiable ledger that can record transactions of digital assets. Different blockchain flavours offer different scalability, security, and potential **privacy** issues. Examples of privacy issues are transaction **linkability**, **data privacy**, and GDPR compliance. Research takes place in the area of resolving privacy issues by allowing blockchain users to act

¹⁷ <https://hyperledger-fabric.readthedocs.io/en/latest/blockchain.html>

¹⁸ <https://hyperledger-fabric.readthedocs.io/en/release-1.4/whatis.html>

anonymously, to take control of their personal data, and to keep private data confidential (J. Bernal Bernabe, 2019).

Figure 24 Smart contracts being written to the ledger.

A **smart contract** is a self-executable program running on the blockchain. It can be seen as a **stored procedure**. A smart contract can update a ledger, store variables, and instantiate and invoke other smart contracts¹⁹. It consists of **pre-defined rules** specified between two or multiple parties. This allows the execution of distributed and automated workflows (Stahnke, 2020). A smart contract is a script describing proper interaction with the ledger. A smart contract provides a well-defined set of ways by which the ledger can be queried or updated. Smart contracts allow data to be shared with integrity, accessibility, and mutability while ensuring that these data can only be manipulated according to the rules stated in that smart contract. Only the entities that agree with the smart contract conditions interact with the smart contract. Smart contracts are often written to ensure fairness between participating entities **without need for a trusted third party** (Zupan, 2020). The author creates the smart contract and publishes it in the blockchain. **Conditions** written in the smart contract prior to HLF could not be **changed** even by the owner after publishing it in the blockchain, but current HLF versions allow updating the smart contract. The conditions stated in the smart contract are enforced by the code and the underlying blockchain system's consensus mechanism, where the **results** are **verified** by the participating nodes.

There are many languages to write smart contracts in. For instance, Ethereum supports a Turing-complete scripting language called Solidity for smart contracts. In Hyperledger Fabric, general-purpose programming languages, like Go and Node.js, can be used to write so-called chaincode.

5.2.3 Encrypted Traffic Analysis

Encrypted network traffic has been steadily growing in volume in recent years, compared to nonencrypted traffic. This presents a challenge to the task of acquiring insight into the nature of the traffic, since network packet payload contents are not visible.

Traditional network traffic analysis techniques use machine learning methods to identify patterns in network flows. Anomaly detection systems can identify attacks against ICS networks in a proactive manner, reporting any suspicious activities. A major disadvantage of such systems is their focus on clear-text packet payloads only. Considering the proliferation of encrypted network traffic, such approaches are bound to become obsolete. For this reason, techniques for network traffic analysis need to focus on detecting patterns in network flows based on other approaches, such as using metadata found in packet headers.

Encrypted traffic analysis in the COLLABS framework will be achieved through the interaction of tools and components developed within three project tasks (T2.2, T2.3 and T2.5), as illustrated in Figure 25:

¹⁹ <https://hyperledger-fabric.readthedocs.io/en/latest/smartcontract/smartcontract.html>

Pattern-based encrypted traffic analysis (Section 5.1.2.1), ML-based cognitive security (Section 5.1.2.2), and anomaly detection (Section 5.1.2.3).

Figure 25 Encrypted traffic analysis enablers.

Pattern-based Encrypted Traffic Analysis

Transport layer security (TLS) use is becoming the standard by people and organizations to protect the integrity and confidentiality of their data flows on the internet. IIoT is also in need of secure communication channels and encryption where technically possible. These encrypted channels can be misused by malicious actors to evade detection by security mechanisms such as intrusion detection systems. A novel mechanism will be used to analyse encrypted network traffic and detect attacks using signatures. It will strengthen the data flows trustworthiness by capturing attacks or anomalies inside the encrypted network traffic of the platform and reporting them to the anomaly detection modules. This mechanism will rely on metadata that can be found inside packet headers, including packet lengths, timestamps, directions, and inter-arrival times.

In the training stage publicly available datasets of malicious traffic will be collected which can be used as a base for our malicious traffic dataset. Then multiple variations of attacks will be conducted in our use cases environment and scenarios to further increase our dataset of malicious network traffic. The captured network traffic will be broken into flows and the sequences of packet payload lengths (which remain constant in multiple variations of the same attack) will be turned into signatures. These signatures will contain the fingerprint of certain actions of malicious tools and malware which target or use the TLS protocol. They rely on specific patterns or sequences of packet lengths which remain constant when these tools are used. After the generation of these signatures, they will be used to detect attacks and malicious behaviour in live network traffic and forward alerts to the corresponding modules.

In addition, CISCO's Joy (cisco, 2020) will be used which can break the network traffic into flows and extract information from TLS connections such as the selected cipher suite, the server's certificate, and the public key length. With this information extracted it will be possible to detect if a component or software is using an old and deprecated encryption method which is vulnerable to being cracked by attackers to extract sensitive information. In addition to detecting weak TLS versions, it will be able to detect TLS downgrade attacks, such as FREAK (Beurdouche, et al., 2015) or POODLE (Möller, Duong, & Kotowicz, 2014) or other vulnerabilities like Heartbleed (Synopsis, 2020). By integrating CISCO's JOY inside the network environment it will be possible to verify the integrity and strength of every TLS connection.

In the COLLABS framework, all of the modules and devices will aim to use strong encryption but there is still a residual threat from malicious insider activity or human error. An employee could intentionally or

by mistake install (vulnerable or malicious) software or a bring a device which uses an older or deprecated TLS version or is infected.

ML-based Cognitive Security

The ML-based cognitive security framework (described in more detail in Section 3.1), consisting of two interacting components - the IoT Secure Wireless fingerprinting component and the ML S(N)C optimization and GMS tools - in its initial utilization, will provide increased security at the IoT device level, by enabling automated device identification based on various behavioural features and patterns, as well as threat identification by detecting anomalous device behaviour. The machine learning tools and models developed within the ML-based cognitive security framework can readily be applied to other types of network data to learn to distinguish regular from anomalous patterns in encrypted network traffic.

Anomaly Detection

Anomaly detection as has been done in the past is not ideal for the IIoT model. Installing an IDS system on a device or a group of devices provides each IDS system with a local security view. A new approach will be a distributed and lightweight anomaly detection which will leverage innovative ML techniques covering a wider spectrum and be able to detect attacks on both single devices and network wide.

In addition, several supervised and unsupervised anomaly detection methods will be considered, including methods based on clustering (K-means, DBSCAN), Isolation Forest, Local Outlier Factor, Double Median Absolute Deviation, and Mahalanobis based approaches. This approach will be better suited for an IIoT environment and will be able to detect specific security threats and identify malicious behaviours. More details about the anomaly detection module can be found in Section 4.2.

6. Summary and Conclusion

In this deliverable, a detailed description of the initial results of the work within work package 2 is given. The results have been structured and presented as part of the minimum viable product of the project that has been reached in M12. As described earlier in the document, the COLLABS framework is organized into three levels of security:

- Level 1 - Hardware-enabled and device-level security,
- Level 2 - Inter-device level security based on distributed ledger technologies, and
- Level 3 - Machine learning-based cognitive security level.

Various technologies presented and demonstrated within the deliverable comprise the initial version of COLLABS Level-3 security package for secure digital supply networks.

Work package 2 includes the following six tasks that round up development of the Level-3 security components in accordance with the project requirements.

- T2.1 Tools and methods for secure data sharing,
- T2.2 Trustworthiness of data flows,
- T2.3 Machine learning-based cognitive security framework,
- T2.4 Statistical Analytics and Machine- / Deep-Learning on shared data,
- T2.5 Distributed anomaly detection for Industrial IoT and
- T2.6 Workflow-driven security for supply chain and compliance in manufacturing.

Level-3 security components developed within these tasks include tools and services for:

- secure data sharing,
- trustworthiness of data flows in collaborative manufacturing environments,
- machine learning-based cognitive security framework applied to shared data,
- workflow-driven security framework for supply chain and manufacturing based on distributed ledger.

Security requirements for the COLLABS framework defined within Level-3 include monitoring different data flows originating from connected objects - IIoT devices. For this, we are using advanced cognitive security and anomaly detection mechanisms such as model-based verification and machine and deep learning to detect anomalies. Moreover, COLLABS focuses on edge-based AI solutions and analysis of encrypted network flows. MVP includes initial versions of components that already cover some aspects of these security requirements.

Encrypted traffic analysis mechanisms based on metadata extraction (that in turn / also leverage machine and deep learning techniques applied to datasets obtained by IIoT device fingerprinting) is another requirement that has been partially addressed by the components of the machine learning based cognitive security framework. However, these components, although functional and mutually connected, have not yet been integrated into the MVP version of the framework.

Outlook

Further security requirements at Level-3 have not been covered by the MVP components, but are planned for the future versions of the COLLABS framework. Those requirements are (1) the use of Reservoir computing in combination with (2) deep learning methods to achieve / improve a balance between accuracy and performance applied to various environments from edge to cloud.

As the COLLABS project continues, the components described in this deliverable and the integration between them all will continue to develop. Future updates and developments towards the first integrated prototype will also include machine learning based cognitive security components as a must. Further development will be presented and discussed within the deliverables D2.2 and D2.3 meant to describe further phases of development within work package 2.

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Translation
CSR_XX	Common Security Requirement no. XX (as described in deliverable D1.2)
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
WDSF	Workflow-driven security framework
FHE	Fully Homomorphic Encryption
LHE	Levelled Homomorphic Encryption
MPC	Multi-Party Computation
SIMD	Single Instruction Multiple Data
HE	Homomorphic Encryption
SMC	Secure Multiparty Computation
MS SEAL	Microsoft Simple Encrypted Arithmetic Library
BFV (RNS)	Brakerski/Fan-Vercauteren (Residue Number System)
CKKS (RNS)	Cheon-Kim-Kim-Song (Residue Number System)
HELib	Homomorphic Encryption Library
BGV	Brakerski-Gentry-Vaikuntanathan
HEAAN	Homomorphic Encryption for Arithmetic of Approximate Numbers
NLP	Natural Language Processing
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
ML	Machine Learning
DL	Deep Learning
ML S(N)C	Machine Learning Structured (Non)Convex Optimization

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